

BIOServicES

Linking soil biodiversity and ecosystem functions and services in different land uses: from the identification of drivers, pressures, and climate change resilience to their economic valuation

Title: Identification and Mapping of BIOServicES stakeholders

Deliverable: D1.2

Author: LGI Sustainable

Report

Document summary	
Document Title	Identification and Mapping of BIOServicES stakeholders
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Lead beneficiary	LGI Sustainable Innovations
Deliverable No.	D1.2
Work Package	WP1
Dissemination type	Document, Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Release date	M18 (28/02/2025)
Review date	30/07/2025
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Table of Contents

1	Introduction	11
1.1.	Overview of WP1	11
1.2.	Relation to other Work Packages and Tasks	13
2	Mission Soil: A Soil Deal for Europe	16
2.1.	Stakeholder and citizen engagement in Mission Soil	17
3	BIOservicES Experimental Sites.....	19
4	Stakeholder identification and mapping methodology.....	20
4.1.	Stakeholder identification methodology	20
4.1.1	Pre-identification of stakeholders tool	20
4.1.2	Template completion by experimental site coordinators	31
4.1.3	Understanding needs from work packages.....	31
4.2.	Stakeholder mapping methodology	32
5	Stakeholder identification and mapping per biogeographical region	35
5.1.	Alpine Experimental Sites.....	36
5.2.	Atlantic Experimental Sites	38
5.3.	Boreal Experimental Sites.....	40
5.4.	Continental Experimental Sites.....	42
5.5.	Mediterranean Experimental Sites.....	44
5.6.	Stakeholders identified across the 25 BIOservicES experimental sites 46	
5.7.	Stakeholder identification comparative analysis and key insights.....	48
6	Stakeholder engagement and co-creation activities.....	52
6.1.	Stakeholder engagement and collaboration tools.....	53
6.2.	Limitations & strategies to implement the co-creation activities.....	54
7	Conclusion	55
8	Annex.....	57
8.1.	High-level overview Experimental Sites	57
8.2.	Stakeholder Identification Template	58
8.3.	Stakeholder Identification and mapping per site	59

8.1.1	Stakeholder identification and mapping Alpine sites.....	60
8.1.2	Stakeholder identification and mapping Atlantic sites.....	79
8.1.3	Stakeholder identification and mapping Boreal sites.....	102
8.1.4	Stakeholder identification and mapping Continental sites.....	129
8.1.5	Stakeholder identification and mapping Mediterranean sites.....	145

List of figures

Fig.1:	WP1 overview and task relationships.....	13
Fig.2:	Overall scheme of BIOServicES.....	14
Fig.3:	Objectives of co-creation activities involving stakeholders.....	15
Fig.4:	Schematic view of the EU Mission's: A Soil Deal for Europe intervention.....	17
Fig.5:	BIOServicES Experimental Site.....	19
Fig.6:	Stakeholder mapping matrix.....	34
Fig.7:	Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Alpine experimental sites.....	37
Fig.8:	Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Atlantic experimental sites.....	39
Fig.9:	Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Boreal experimental sites.....	41
Fig.10:	Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Continental experimental sites.....	43
Fig.11:	Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Mediterranean experimental sites.....	45
Fig.12:	Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Alpine agricultural land use site.....	62
Fig.13:	Stakeholder mapping Alpine agricultural land use site.....	63
Fig.14:	Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Alpine forest land use site.....	65
Fig.15:	Stakeholder mapping Alpine forest land use site.....	66
Fig.16:	Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Alpine industrial land use site.....	69
Fig.17:	Stakeholder mapping Alpine industrial land use site.....	70
Fig.18:	Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Alpine semi-natural land use site.....	73
Fig.19:	Stakeholder mapping Alpine semi-natural land use site.....	73
Fig.20:	Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Alpine wetland land use site.....	77

Fig.21: Stakeholder mapping Alpine wetland land use site	78
Fig.22: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Atlantic agricultural land use site	82
Fig.23: Stakeholder mapping Atlantic agricultural land use site	83
Fig.24: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Atlantic mining land use site	87
Fig.25: Stakeholder mapping Atlantic mining land use site	88
Fig.26: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Atlantic semi-natural land use site.....	91
Fig.27: Stakeholder mapping Atlantic semi-natural land use site	92
Fig.28: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Atlantic urban land use site	95
Fig.29: Stakeholder mapping Atlantic urban land use site	96
Fig.30: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Atlantic wetland land use site	100
Fig.31: Stakeholder mapping Atlantic wetland land use site	101
Fig.32: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Boreal agricultural land use site	105
Fig.33: Stakeholder mapping Boreal agricultural land use site	106
Fig.34: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Boreal forest land use site	111
Fig.35: Stakeholder mapping Boreal forest land use site	112
Fig.36: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Boreal mining land use site	116
Fig.37: Stakeholder mapping Boreal mining land use site	117
Fig.38: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Boreal semi-natural land use site.....	122
Fig.39: Stakeholder mapping Boreal semi-natural land use site	123
Fig.40: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Boreal wetland land use site	127
Fig.41: Stakeholder mapping Boreal wetland land use site	128
Fig.42: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Continental agricultural land use site	130
Fig.43: Stakeholder mapping Continental agricultural land use site	131
Fig.44: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Continental forest land use site	134
Fig.45: Stakeholder mapping Continental forest land use site	135
Fig.46: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Continental mining land use site.....	137
Fig.47: Stakeholder mapping Continental mining land use site	138

Fig.48: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Continental semi-natural land use site	140
Fig.49: Stakeholder mapping Continental mining land use site	141
Fig.50: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Continental urban land use site.....	143
Fig.51: Stakeholder mapping Continental urban land use site.....	144
Fig.52: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Mediterranean agricultural land use site	146
Fig.53: Stakeholder mapping Mediterranean agricultural land use site	147
Fig.54: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Mediterranean dryland land use site.....	149
Fig.55: Stakeholder mapping Mediterranean dryland land use site	150
Fig.56: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Mediterranean industrial land use site	152
Fig.57: Stakeholder mapping Mediterranean industrial land use site	153
Fig.58: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Mediterranean mining land use site.....	155
Fig.59: Stakeholder mapping Mediterranean mining land use site	156
Fig.60: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Mediterranean urban land use site.....	158
Fig.61: Stakeholder mapping Mediterranean urban land use site	159

List of tables

Table 1: Pre-identification of stakeholders for agricultural land use	23
Table 2: Pre-identification of stakeholders for dryland land use.....	24
Table 3: Pre-identification of stakeholders for forest land use	25
Table 4: Pre-identification of stakeholders for industrial land use.....	26
Table 5: Pre-identification of stakeholders for mining land use.....	27
Table 6: Pre-identification of stakeholders for urban land use	28
Table 7: Pre-identification of stakeholders for semi-natural land use.....	29
Table 8: Pre- identification of stakeholders for wetland land use.....	30
Table 9: Comparative analysis stakeholder categories per biogeographical region	50
Table 10: Comparative analysis stakeholder categories per land use	51
Table 11: Alpine agricultural land use site	60
Table 12: Stakeholder identification Alpine agricultural land use site.....	61
Table 13: Alpine forest land use site	64
Table 14: Stakeholder identification Alpine forest land use site	65
Table 15: Alpine industrial land use site	67
Table 16: Stakeholder identification Alpine industrial land use site.....	68
Table 17: Alpine semi-natural land use site	71
Table 18: Stakeholder identification Alpine semi-natural land use site	72
Table 19: Alpine wetland land use site.....	75
Table 20: Stakeholder identification Alpine wetland land use site	76
Table 21: Atlantic agricultural land use site.....	79
Table 22: Stakeholder identification Atlantic agricultural land use site.....	81
Table 23: Atlantic mining land use site	85
Table 24: Stakeholder identification Atlantic mining land use site	86
Table 25: Atlantic semi-natural land use site.....	89
Table 26: Stakeholder identification Atlantic semi-natural land use site	91
Table 27: Atlantic urban land use site.....	93
Table 28: Stakeholder identification Atlantic urban land use site	95
Table 29: Atlantic wetland land use site.....	98
Table 30: Stakeholder identification Atlantic wetland land use site	100
Table 31: Boreal agricultural land use site	102
Table 32: Stakeholder identification Boreal agricultural land use site.....	104
Table 33: Boreal forest land use site	108
Table 34: Stakeholder identification Boreal forest land use site	110
Table 35: Boreal mining land use site	113
Table 36: Stakeholder identification Boreal mining land use site.....	116
Table 37: Boreal semi-natural land use site	119
Table 38: Stakeholder identification Boreal semi-natural land use site.....	121

Table 39: Boreal wetland land use site	124
Table 40: Stakeholder identification Boreal wetland land use site	126
Table 41: Continental agricultural land use site	129
Table 42: Stakeholder identification Continental agricultural land use site....	130
Table 43: Continental forest land use site	133
Table 44: Stakeholder identification Continental forest land use site	134
Table 45: Continental mining land use site	136
Table 46: Stakeholder identification Continental mining land use site.....	137
Table 47: Continental semi-natural land use site	139
Table 48: Stakeholder identification Continental semi-natural land use site	140
Table 49: Continental urban land use site	142
Table 50: Stakeholder identification Continental urban land use site.....	143
Table 51: Mediterranean agricultural land use site	145
Table 52: Stakeholder identification Mediterranean agricultural land use site	146
Table 53: Mediterranean dryland land use site	148
Table 54: Stakeholder identification Mediterranean dryland land use site.....	149
Table 55: Mediterranean industrial land use site	151
Table 56: Stakeholder identification Mediterranean industrial land use site...152	
Table 57: Mediterranean mining land use site	154
Table 58: Stakeholder identification Mediterranean mining land use site.....155	
Table 59: Mediterranean urban land use site	157
Table 60: Stakeholder identification Mediterranean urban land use site	158

Executive summary

The main objective of BIOservicES is to understand interconnections between soil organisms and the delivery of multiple soil ecosystem functions and services at different scale. By generating new knowledge and indicators based on soil organisms, ecosystem functions, and services, BIOservicES aims to support the maintenance and enhancement of soil health across Europe. The project has 25 experimental sites across 8 land uses and 5 biogeographic regions in Europe: Alpine (Switzerland), Atlantic (Spain), Boreal (Latvia), Continental (Germany) and Mediterranean (Spain). The project, including the 25 experimental sites, stakeholders and partners, will act as a hub for co-creation, co-design and co-learning.

This deliverable aims to systematically identify and map key stakeholders for each experimental site, ensuring their effective engagement in the BIOservicES project. By analysing stakeholder dynamics across different land uses and biogeographic regions, it provides insights into how different actors contribute to soil health initiatives. In total 400 stakeholders are identified. The different stakeholder types are categorized across 8 distinct categories:

1. Civil society organisations
2. Education, Research
3. Finance & Business
4. Media
5. Public bodies
6. Residents, Citizens
7. Suppliers & Clients
8. Workers & Farmers

Stakeholder identification and mapping serve as a foundation for co-creation activities, as they ensure that all relevant groups, including farmers, land managers, policymakers, researchers, and industry representatives, are effectively involved in shaping project outcomes. This identification process is a continuous process and WP1 will continue to work with site coordinators to ensure all categories are well represented across each biogeographical region.

The deliverable further supports the project's broader objectives to improving soil health practices and policies by enabling a structured and strategic approach to stakeholder engagement. A well-mapped stakeholder network allows for better alignment between stakeholder interests and project goals, fostering an environment where knowledge exchange, innovation, and

collaboration can thrive. Additionally, stakeholders benefit from participation by gaining access to scientific knowledge, innovative practices, and collaborative networks that support sustainable land management. This ensures that the project results are practical, relevant, and widely adopted by different stakeholder groups.

This deliverable presents the stakeholder identification and mapping methodology and results of the project. A key component of this is the stakeholder pre-identification tool, which categorizes stakeholders based on land-use. This tool, outlined in the methodology section, can also be adopted by other soil health projects seeking to systematically identify relevant stakeholders for their sites. Furthermore, this deliverable includes the stakeholder identification and mapping results for each biogeographic region and its associated experimental sites. The results provide a detailed distribution of stakeholder types per region and per site, clearly illustrating how each site connects to various stakeholder groups. Additionally, a stakeholder map is provided for each site, classifying stakeholders by their influence over the site and their interest in the project. These findings will guide future co-creation activities, ensuring that the right stakeholders are engaged in meaningful collaborations that enhance the project's impact.

In conclusion, the stakeholder identification and mapping process revealed significant variations in stakeholder presence across different sites, highlighting the diverse roles and priorities associated with different land uses. The pre-identification of stakeholders based on land use characteristics serves as a valuable tool for categorizing and referencing stakeholders within specific groups. This approach not only facilitates a more structured engagement process, ensuring that the project's results are grounded in real-life cases, but also supports the effective local implementation of soil health practices and policies. As stakeholder engagement is a fundamental aspect of soil health projects funded by the European Commission, this report introduces a more standardized and robust methodology for stakeholder identification and mapping across different projects.

1 Introduction

This deliverable is part of *Task 1.1 Identification and mapping of stakeholders*. The task leader is LGI Sustainable Innovation, in collaboration with Zabala Innovation, and all partners contributing by providing inputs for stakeholders identification. Main contributors are the experimental site coordinators, who form the direct connection between the consortium and experimental sites. The main objective of Task 1.1 is to identify and map stakeholders of the 25 experimental sites, taking into account other EU and international R&I initiatives.

The identification and mapping of stakeholders is vital to fostering their engagement during the co-design and co-creation activities across the various work packages. This deliverable serves as a report compiling the identified stakeholders and stakeholder groups of all 25 experimental sites and present

a comprehensive overview of all experimental sites, detailing their geographical context and unique characteristics. To enrich the information on each site, it includes a list of stakeholders identified by the Experimental Site coordinators. These stakeholders are then systematically mapped to highlight their interests and levels of influence on the BIOservicES project. This mapping also aids in identifying their roles in co-design and co-creation activities throughout the project timeline.

The Deliverable is divided as follows:

- An introduction to WP1 and this deliverable
- Explanation of A Soil Deal for Europe and stakeholder engagement
- BIOservicES' experimental sites
- Stakeholder engagement and mapping methodology
- Stakeholder engagement and mapping results
- Stakeholders for co-creation and co-design activities

1.1.Overview of WP1

WP1 is committed to strengthen and/or create stakeholder communities along the project.

The WP1 objectives are:

- O1.1. Strengthen and/or create Communities of Stakeholders (COSs) along the project experimental sites, EU and international initiatives and organizations (Tasks 1.1 and 1.2).
- O1.2. Organize engagement activities for codesign, co-creation and co-learning involving the COSs (Task 1.3).
- O1.3. Develop a digital platform to ensure an effective collaboration of COSs for the short- and long-term growth and sustainability of the experimental sites that enables co-creation, co-innovation and co-learning processes (Task 1.4).

Figure 1 provides a visual overview on how WP1 is divided in tasks. Milestone MS1 (M18) and Deliverable D1.2 both belong to T1.1, and form the baseline to build a community of stakeholders (T1.2), animate co-design and co-creation activities with these stakeholders (T1.3) and engage the stakeholders through the collaborative platform (T1.4).

Task 1.1 lays the groundwork by providing a foundational understanding of how each experimental site is structured in relation to its stakeholders, clarifying their roles, relationships, and positioning within the broader value chain. Building on this, Task 1.2 opens up avenues for more strategic dialogue, enabling a clearer understanding of both site-specific and stakeholder needs and challenges. This creates opportunities for meaningful collaboration and long-term engagement. While Task 1.1 establishes the necessary knowledge base, Task 1.2 acts as a strategic roadmap to identify those experimental sites with the greatest potential to evolve into Living Labs over the course of the project. Once the current state of each experimental site is assessed through Task 1.2, stakeholders identified in Task 1.1 can be mobilized to support the site in achieving the operational framework of a Living Lab. In particular, stakeholders classified as having both high influence and high interest in the project and the site should be engaged to play an active and guiding role in this process. The activities designed to support sites in this learning process and in identifying their transformation opportunities are detailed in Deliverable D1.1 under Task 1.2.

Additionally, the specific needs of each work package in relation to stakeholders' engagement will be collected and analysed. Each work package lead is in contact with the LGI team in order to exchange ideas on stakeholder engagement (T1.3). These conversations will help transform the needs of all WP leaders into concrete work sessions, workshops and active stakeholder participation. Information on co-creation activities will be collected later to feed the deliverable on co-organized engagement activities (D1.4).

In parallel with T1.1, discussions are underway to understand the needs of internal partners, external advisory partners, experimental site stakeholders, and individuals interested in soil health. These insights will guide the development of the collaborative [SoilCommunity platform](#), funded by the InBestSoil and BIOservicES projects, fostering effective collaboration and engagement throughout the project (T1.4).

Fig.1: WP1 overview and task relationships

1.2.Relation to other Work Packages and Tasks

The primary objective of WP1 is to support the project's stakeholder engagement needs, benefiting both its specific tasks and the broader objectives of other Work Packages. Establishing strong stakeholder communities serves as a foundational goal for the entire project, creating a collaborative network that enhances the work and research activities across all tasks. This interconnected community (Figure 2) not only facilitates ongoing collaboration but also strengthens the impact and reach of BIOservicES partners, ensuring that each Work Package can leverage stakeholder insights and participation to maximize project outcomes.

Fig.2: Overall scheme of BIOServicES

The different work packages in BIOServicES will be conducting various co-design and co-creation activities through surveys, workshops, presentations and more. Stakeholder identification and engagement is a two-way process: it helps the project understand which stakeholders can provide valuable insights for these activities, while also clarifying how the project's outcomes can benefit them. By understanding stakeholders' expertise and interests, partners can involve those who contribute meaningfully to topics such as soil sampling, soil indicators, soil policies, soil biodiversity, pressures and drivers on soil health, and the economic valuation and business models related to soil ecosystems. Simultaneously, this approach ensures that the project's findings are relevant and useful, enhancing stakeholders' work in these critical areas. Overall, effectively identifying and mapping stakeholders is essential for understanding their roles in co-design and co-creation activities, which are critical to ensuring the project's success.

Why co-creation, co-innovation, and co-learnings:

1. Ensuring that the scientific methods used are aligned with the reality on the ground.
2. Encouraging stakeholders to participate in the selection of indicators, metrics, etc., allows for empowering stakeholders and avoids analytical biases centred around a specific type of data that might be easier or less representative of reality.
3. Allowing stakeholders to feel involved at each stage and reinstating the human element in their ability to take action at each step (research, application, dissemination, for example).
4. Involving various types of stakeholders also fosters synergy and enables true innovation in the way of working, proposed solutions, and even knowledge dissemination to achieve, by the project's end, a greater impact (at least on knowledge).

Fig.3: Objectives of co-creation activities involving stakeholders

2 Mission Soil: A Soil Deal for Europe

The EU Mission "A Soil Deal for Europe" is part of the European Union's broader missions framework, which focuses on addressing key challenges in improving soil health across the EU to ensure a sustainable future for agriculture, biodiversity, climate resilience, and overall ecosystem health. Launched under the Horizon Europe program, this mission leads the transition towards healthy soils by:

- Funding an ambitious research and innovation program with a strong social science component
- Putting in place an effective network of 100 living labs and lighthouses to co-create knowledge, test solutions and demonstrate their value in real-life conditions
- Developing a harmonized framework for soil monitoring in Europe
- Raising people's awareness on the vital importance of soils

The mission soil has 8 main objectives:

- reduce desertification
- conserve soil organic carbon stocks
- stop soil sealing and increase re-use of urban soils
- reduce soil pollution and enhance restoration
- prevent erosion
- improve soil structure to enhance soil biodiversity
- reduce the EU global footprint on soils
- improve soil literacy in society

Fig.4: Schematic view of the EU Mission's: A Soil Deal for Europe intervention

2.1. Stakeholder and citizen engagement in Mission Soil

To achieve its eight objectives, the European Commission has structured the "Soil Deal for Europe" around four core operational pillars. A key pillar among them focuses on engaging soil user communities and the broader society, aiming to foster inclusive, widespread participation and collaboration. This engagement pillar seeks to actively involve stakeholders and citizens in the mission, enhancing awareness of soil health issues throughout the EU and promoting hands-on participation to achieve local and regional objectives. By mobilizing actors from across society - including government bodies, local communities, scientists, environmental organizations, farmers, and industry representatives - this pillar facilitates the creation of networks to share knowledge, drive innovation, and encourage collaborative efforts toward the common EU goal of sustainable soil health.

WPI within the BIOServicES project directly contributes to this engagement pillar by systematically identifying and engaging stakeholders linked to the project's 25 experimental sites. These stakeholders, spanning local, regional, and even national level, bring essential expertise, interests, and influence to the project. WPI ensures that the perspectives and contributions of diverse soil users, such as agricultural practitioners, policy advisors, conservationists, and

business representatives, are incorporated into the project. Through this, WPI not only builds a network that aligns with the mission's goals but also strengthens local connections, fosters community involvement, and enriches the project with real-world insights that reflect a variety of soil-related challenges and opportunities.

Ultimately, WPI's efforts in identifying and involving stakeholders serve as a bridge between the BIOServicES project and the broader objectives of the Soil Deal mission, ensuring that local actions and stakeholder expertise contribute meaningfully to the EU's commitment to achieving healthy soils and sustainable soil management across Europe.

3 BIOSERVICES Experimental Sites

To effectively identify and map stakeholders, it is crucial first to understand the unique context of each experimental site. The BIOSERVICES project encompasses 25 experimental sites spanning eight land uses across five biogeographic regions in Europe. These sites serve as the focal points for soil sampling and testing activities, as well as hubs for co-creation, co-design, and co-learning. The biogeographic regions represented include the Alpine (Switzerland), Atlantic (Spain), Boreal (Latvia), Continental (Germany), and Mediterranean (Spain) regions.

This section outlines the context of these experimental sites to provide a comprehensive understanding before diving into stakeholder identification. Each site, with its distinct characteristics, offers valuable insights that help refine the selection of appropriate indicators and sampling methodologies. Collaborating closely with these sites enables the project to align its analysis with local realities, facilitating the development of tailored solutions for enhancing soil health across Europe's diverse biogeographic contexts.

Figure 5 illustrates the experimental sites selected for this project. The experimental sites were selected to showcase sustainable management practices that have improved soil health, positioned next to areas where less sustainable practices or significant pressures have resulted in soil degradation and lower soil health. Each experimental site is defined by distinct attributes and environmental pressures. The stakeholder identification and mapping section will provide a detailed overview of each site, outlining its specific mission and contributions to mitigating soil health pressures through soil health practices. This ensures a clear connection between site characteristics and the stakeholders involved. For a more concise summary, Annex 8.1 provides an overview of all experimental sites, highlighting key characteristics such as soil pressures, soil types, and vegetation.

Fig.5: BIOSERVICES Experimental Site

4 Stakeholder identification and mapping methodology

This section presents the methodology developed and applied for stakeholder identification, and next, for stakeholder mapping. This methodology is based on a methodology developed under the EU Project InBestSoil (D2.2 Stakeholder Identification and mapping): [Stakeholder mapping for Lighthouses and Living labs](#). Given the close collaboration of projects it makes sense to align the methodologies and use a similar analysis.

4.1. Stakeholder identification methodology

Stakeholder engagement is a vital part of the BIOServicES project to ensure the effectiveness of co-creation, co-innovation and co-learning in soil health. The stakeholder engagement plan will connect local communities composed of various stakeholder groups, including farmers, foresters, industries, public authorities etc. Identifying the correct stakeholders is crucial to facilitate activities related to the harmonization of methods for soil sampling and analyses.

Each experimental site has an associated project partner, known as an experimental site coordinator, that will interact with the stakeholders to collect data, validate information and disseminate results. These experimental site coordinators facilitate the contact with the experimental sites and stakeholders and ensure their interest is achieved.

Stakeholder identification was conducted continuously throughout the project's first year. The initial high-level stakeholder identification led to the achievement of our first milestone, MS1. By regularly updating this identification process, a more comprehensive stakeholder list is provided in this Deliverable. However, as stakeholder identification and mapping are ongoing activities throughout the project, the list of stakeholders will be continuously refined and expanded over the project's duration.

4.1.1 Pre-identification of stakeholders tool

The stakeholder identification process was conducted using a stakeholder identification template created by LGI. To create the template (displayed in annex 8.2), LGI carried out an initial desk review on the various regions and land uses to pre-identify stakeholder groups and profiles that could be relevant during the project. For each type of land use (Agricultural, Urban, Industrial, Mining, Dryland, Forest, Wetland, Semi-natural), different stakeholder groups were identified. This stakeholder research is a key part to the overall identification process, as it acknowledges that stakeholder types may differ across land uses and encourages experimental site coordinators to think about key stakeholders connected to the sites mission

and outcomes. To facilitate the classification process, stakeholders were pre-identified and categorized into eight distinct groups:

- **Civil society organisations:** Civil society organizations, for example, can include NGOs and advocacy groups focused on environmental conservation
- **Education, Research:** Education and research stakeholders may consist of universities, research institutions, and experts studying topics such as sustainable land management, mining impacts, and biodiversity conservation
- **Finance & Business:** Finance and business stakeholders might include banks, investors, and companies directly funding the site
- **Media:** Media stakeholders, such as journalists and news agencies, help shape public perception and policy discussions on land use issues
- **Public bodies:** Public bodies can refer to government agencies, municipalities, and regulatory authorities overseeing land policies in sectors like mining, agriculture, and urban planning
- **Residents, Citizens:** Residents and citizens typically include local communities living near or using the land
- **Suppliers & Clients:** Suppliers and clients could range from agricultural input providers and buyers to industrial supply chains and mining contractors
- **Workers & Farmers:** Workers and farmers may encompass labourers, agricultural workers, and miners directly engaged in land-based industries, shaping the site through their daily activities

By conducting this initial desk research, potential stakeholder types were identified connected to the unique characteristics of each experimental site. This step is essential for identifying the stakeholders who are most relevant to the different land uses in the project. For example, agricultural land use sites are likely to involve stakeholders such as farmers, agricultural producers, and suppliers of fertilizers and machinery, all of whom are directly engaged with or impacted by the agricultural activities on the land. On the other hand, wetland sites may attract stakeholders from local watershed and water resources management authorities, while forest land uses could involve timber industry clients who purchase the wood.

Although each site may have distinct stakeholder types, it is important to recognize that some stakeholders may span multiple experimental sites. Research organizations, for instance, can connect to different sites based on their research needs and objectives. Stakeholder groups being present in

multiple land use sites can also highlight their importance in the project's overall goals. These stakeholders are not only engaged with specific sites, but their perspectives and input might be valuable in shaping the project's overarching strategies and outcomes. In contrast, other stakeholders might be more closely tied to one specific land use, with their role and impact being more unique to that particular land use. For example, local farmers or agricultural producers are directly impacted by and engaged with the agricultural practices on a specific experimental site, and their interests and concerns are largely tied to the characteristics of that site. Their influence, while critical in the context of agricultural sites, might not extend to other land uses like wetlands or forests. Instead these stakeholders bring in-depth, specialized knowledge and expertise to the land use they are connected to, which is essential for addressing the unique challenges and opportunities within that specific context.

The pre-identification process not only ensures that partners capture a broad and diverse range of relevant stakeholders, but also enables us to tailor our engagement strategies. By understanding the specific interests, needs, and influences of each stakeholder type, partners can foster more effective, context-specific engagement that aligns with the objectives of the project.

Lastly, since stakeholder engagement serves as a fundamental pillar of the Soil Deal for Europe and most projects under this mission include a dedicated work package for stakeholder engagement, the pre-identification of stakeholders based on various land uses can act as a high-level methodology or tool to guide other projects in identifying their stakeholders effectively. Tables 1 to 8 present the various stakeholder types pre-identified for each category, associated with the respective land uses.

Agricultural Land Use: Pre-stakeholder identification

Categories	Type of stakeholders
Workers & Farmers	<p>Site responsible Owners and managers of the agricultural site</p> <p>Farmers and agricultural producers (livestock owners included)</p> <p>Workers, former workers</p> <p>Landscaping companies</p>
Community of workers	<p>Agricultural Industry Associations</p> <p>Labor Unions and syndicate</p>
Suppliers, clients	<p>Suppliers and subcontractors (i.e. agricultural inputs, seeds, fertilizers, equipment...)</p> <p>Transport and logistics companies</p> <p>Trade association</p> <p>Direct clients (cooperatives, farmers organizations...)</p> <p>Indirect clients (retailers, consumers...)</p>
Residents, citizens	<p>Local residents' associations</p> <p>Rural Communities and Residents organizations</p>
External ecosystem, pressure, laws, health laws (public bodies and civil society organisations)	<p>Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)</p> <p>Environmental and Conservation Organizations (environmental impacts of Agri practices and could advocate for sustainable and ecofriendly farming.)</p> <p>Land Developers and Real Estate Interests (can be interested in land use decisions for other purpose such as urban or commercial development)</p> <p>NGO on agricultural or rural development</p> <p>Health bodies</p>
Education, Research	<p>Research bodies</p> <p>Academics in agricultural, environmental science and economics</p> <p>Soil experts</p>
Finance & Business	<p>Finance partners</p> <p>Eco or nature tourism</p>
Media	<p>Local media and bloggers</p> <p>Agricultural newspapers</p>

Table 1: Pre-identification of stakeholders for agricultural land use

Dryland Land Use: Pre-stakeholder identification

Categories	Type of stakeholders
Workers & Farmers	Site responsible Owners and managers of the dryland site Farmers and agricultural producers (livestock owners included) Workers, former workers Landscaping companies
Community of workers	Agricultural Industry Associations Labor Unions and syndicate
Suppliers, clients	Suppliers and subcontractors (i.e. agricultural inputs, seeds, fertilizers, equipment...) Transport and logistics companies Trade association Direct clients Indirect clients
Residents, citizens	Local residents' associations Rural Communities and Residents organizations
External ecosystem, pressure, laws, health laws (public bodies and civil society organisations)	Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national) Environmental and Conservation Organizations (environmental impacts of agricultural practices and could advocate for sustainable and ecofriendly farming.) Land Developers and Real Estate Interests (can be interested in land use decisions for other purpose such as urban or commercial development) NGO on agricultural or rural development Health bodies
Education, Research	Research bodies Academics in agricultural, environmental science and economics Soil experts
Finance & Business	Finance partners Eco or nature tourism
Media	Local media and bloggers Industrial newspapers

Table 2: Pre-identification of stakeholders for dryland land use

Forest Land Use: Pre-stakeholder identification

Categories	Type of stakeholders
Workers & Farmers	Site responsible Owners and managers of forest site Forestry and Logging companies Workers, former workers Landscaping companies
Community of workers	Timber Industry Associations Labor Unions and syndicate
Suppliers, clients	Suppliers and subcontractors (i.e. timber sticks, vegetal materials, fertilizers, equipment...) Transport and logistics companies Energy & Biomass Industry (companies of) Watershed and Water resources Management authorities Direct clients (cooperatives, wood transformation organizations...) Indirect clients (retailers, wood consumers...)
Residents, citizens	Local residents' associations Rural Communities and Residents organizations Hunters and wildlife enthusiasts (all ppl who have an interest of wildlife conservation)
External ecosystem, pressure, laws, health laws (public bodies and civil society organisations)	Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national) Environmental and Conservation Organizations (environmental impacts of agricultural practices and could advocate for sustainable and ecofriendly farming.) Land Developers and Real Estate Interests (can be interested in land use decisions for other purpose such as urban or commercial development) NGO on climate change and carbon offset projects Fire management and disaster response authorities Health bodies
Education, Research	Research bodies Academics in agricultural, silviculture, environmental science Soil experts
Finance & Business	Finance partners and carbon offset and Climate change mitigation organization Eco or nature tourism
Media	Local media and bloggers Sylviculture, forestry newspapers

Table 3: Pre-identification of stakeholders for forest land use

Industrial Land Use: Pre-stakeholder identification

Categories	Type of stakeholders
Workers & Farmers	Site responsible Owners and managers of the industrial site Workers, former workers Landscaping companies
Community of workers	Industry Associations Labor Unions and syndicate
Suppliers, clients	Suppliers and subcontractors Transport and logistics companies Direct clients Indirect clients
Residents, citizens	Local residents' associations Citizens and citizen organizations Neighbours
External ecosystem, pressure, laws, health laws (public bodies and civil society organisations)	Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national) Environmental protection agencies (footprint regulation, observatory...) Health bodies
Education, Research	Economic development bodies Research bodies Academics in industry (industrial exploitation, industrial waste treatment...) Soil experts
Finance & Business	Finance partners Eco or nature tourism
Media	Local media and bloggers Industrial newspapers

Table 4: Pre-identification of stakeholders for industrial land us

Mining Land Use: Pre-stakeholder identification

Categories	Type of stakeholders
Workers & Farmers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Site responsible Owners and managers of the mining site Mining companies Workers, former workers Landscaping companies to fulfil compulsory compensation Landscaping companies (after exploitation time?)
Community of workers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mining companies Associations Labor Unions and syndicate
Suppliers, clients	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Suppliers and subcontractors (i.e. mining inputs, chemicals...) Transport and logistics companies Trade association Water and waste treatment enterprise Direct clients (cooperatives, farmers organizations...) Indirect clients (retailers, consumers...)
Residents, citizens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local residents' associations Rural Communities and Residents organizations Neighbours impacted (upstream and downstream)
External ecosystem, pressure, laws, health laws (public bodies and civil society organisations)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national) Environmental and Conservation Organizations (environmental impacts of Agri practices and could advocate for sustainable and ecofriendly farming.) NGO on rural development Health bodies
Education, Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research bodies Academics in environment, geology Soil experts
Finance & Business	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Finance partners Local tourism (can be influenced by mining landscape)
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local media and bloggers Environmental newspapers

Table 5: Pre-identification of stakeholders for mining land use

Urban Land Use: Pre-stakeholder identification

Categories	Type of stakeholders
Workers & Farmers	Site responsible / owners and entities owning the area Urban planning firm Companies working on this site Urban farmers Landscaping companies
Community of workers	Community gardeners
Suppliers, clients	
Residents, citizens	Local residents' associations Citizens and citizen organizations Neighbours
External ecosystem, pressure, laws, health laws (public bodies and civil society organisations)	Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national) Environmental and Conservation Organizations (environmental impacts of urban activities) Health bodies
Education, Research	Research bodies Academics in urban design and policy makers Soil experts
Finance & Business	Finance partners
Media	Local media and bloggers

Table 6: Pre-identification of stakeholders for urban land use

Semi-natural Land Use: Pre-stakeholder identification

Categories	Type of stakeholders
Workers & Farmers	<p>Site responsible Owners and managers of the site</p> <p>Farmers and agricultural producers (livestock owners included) or any type of producers working on this area</p> <p>Workers, former workers</p> <p>Landscaping companies</p>
Community of workers	
Suppliers, clients	<p>Suppliers and subcontractors</p> <p>Transport and logistics companies</p> <p>Trade association</p> <p>Watershed and Water resources Management authorities</p>
Residents, citizens	<p>Local residents' associations</p> <p>Rural Communities and Residents organizations</p> <p>Hunters and wildlife enthusiasts (all ppl who have an interest of wildlife conservation)</p>
External ecosystem, pressure, laws, health laws (public bodies and civil society organisations)	<p>Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)</p> <p>Environmental and Conservation Organizations (environmental impacts of agricultural practices and could advocate for sustainable and ecofriendly farming.)</p> <p>Land Developers and Real Estate Interests (can be interested in land use decisions for other purpose such as urban or commercial development)</p> <p>NGO on agricultural or rural development</p> <p>Health bodies</p>
Education, Research	<p>Research bodies</p> <p>Academics in agricultural, environmental science and economics</p> <p>Soil experts</p>
Finance & Business	<p>Finance partners</p> <p>Eco or nature tourism (birdwatching, hunting, wildlife photography...)</p> <p>Recreational and tourism industry (skiing, tourism infrastructures...)</p> <p>Fire management and disaster response authorities</p>
Media	<p>Local media and bloggers</p>

Table 7: Pre-identification of stakeholders for semi-natural land use

Wetland Land Use: Pre-stakeholder identification

Categories	Type of stakeholders
Workers & Farmers	<p>Site responsible Owners and managers of the wetland site</p> <p>Farmers and agricultural producers (livestock owners included)</p> <p>Workers, former workers</p> <p>Peat exploitation companies</p> <p>Fishermen and aquaculture operators</p>
Community of workers	<p>Aquaculture agricultural Associations</p> <p>Labor Unions and syndicate</p>
Suppliers, clients	Watershed and Water resources Management authorities
Residents, citizens	<p>Local residents' associations</p> <p>Rural Communities and Residents organizations</p> <p>Hunters and wildlife enthusiasts (all ppl who have an interest of wildlife conservation)</p>
External ecosystem, pressure, laws, health laws (public bodies and civil society organisations)	<p>Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)</p> <p>Environmental and Conservation Organizations (environmental impacts of agricultural practices and could advocate for sustainable, and ecofriendly farming.)</p> <p>Land Developers and Real Estate Interests (can be interested in land use decisions for other purpose such as urban or commercial development)</p> <p>NGO on agricultural or rural development</p> <p>Health bodies</p>
Education, Research	<p>Research bodies</p> <p>Academics in agricultural, environmental science and economics</p> <p>Soil experts</p>
Finance & Business	<p>Finance partners</p> <p>Eco or nature tourism (birdwatching, hunting, wildlife photography...)</p>
Media	<p>Local media and bloggers</p> <p>Aquaculture newspapers</p>

Table 8: Pre- identification of stakeholders for wetland land use

4.1.2 Template completion by experimental site coordinators

Based on this desk research and the pre-identification of stakeholders per land use, LGI created an excel template for each experimental site coordinator to identify the most relevant stakeholders for each site. The template includes a detailed explanation on how to fill it in.

To guide partners in identifying the relevant stakeholders, LGI proposed three steps:

1. Experimental site coordinators were first asked to provide a detailed overview of each experimental site to understand the site's characteristics and overall context
2. Experimental site coordinators were asked to identify the first stakeholders, providing their contact details, organisation and the overall influence and interest they might have for BIOServicES
3. If experimental site coordinators were unable to provide specific information on stakeholders, they could provide an indication or leave questions open for future discussion

For each selected stakeholder, coordinators were able to provide their general information including: the organisation's name, the contact details, a description of stakeholder actions and the influence and interest of the stakeholder on the project. While additional stakeholder details can enhance understanding of profiles, including contact information was not required, as the document aims to provide an overview of stakeholders rather than serve as a contact directory. For reference, Annex 8.2 provide an overview of the excel template used by experimental site coordinators to identify relevant stakeholders.

Next to sending the template to be filled in, LGI offered one to one meetings with partners to collaboratively fill in the document to discuss the stakeholder selection. This allowed partners to ask questions and refine the data of identified stakeholders.

The stakeholder identification template will remain used throughout the project, allowing experimental site coordinators to continuously add relevant stakeholders depending on project ad experimental site activities.

4.1.3 Understanding needs from work packages

Given that the stakeholder identification process forms the foundation for effective stakeholder engagement throughout the project's timeline, it is essential to understand the project's engagement needs during the identification phase. This ensures the selection of the most relevant and impactful stakeholders. To achieve a comprehensive understanding of BIOServicES' stakeholder engagement needs and activities, LGI conducted semi-structured interviews with WP leaders under Task 1.3. These interviews

were instrumental in clarifying the requirements for each work package, offering valuable insights into how stakeholders could actively contribute to the project's success while also benefiting from its outcomes. Since Task 1.1 (Stakeholder Identification and Mapping) is conducted in parallel with Task 1.3 (Animation of Co-design, Co-creation, and Co-learning Activities), the meetings held under Task 1.3 played a supportive role in the stakeholder identification process. This synergy between the two tasks allows for a more dynamic and iterative approach to both stakeholder identification and engagement, facilitating more effective collaboration throughout the project lifecycle. Based on insights from interviews with WP leaders, experimental site coordinators were better prepared to identify targeted activities - such as surveys, workshops, and interviews - that aligned with stakeholders' interests and fostered their active participation.

4.2. Stakeholder mapping methodology

One key objective of WP1 is to create stakeholder communities for co-design, co-creation, and co-learning activities. To encourage community interaction and facilitate the engagement of stakeholders, it is important to map stakeholders across similar characteristics in order to understand their role and impact in the project.

Stakeholders were identified for each of the 25 experimental sites, spanning eight distinct land-use types: Agriculture, Urban, Industrial, Wetland, Dryland, Semi-natural, Mining, and Forest. Using a structured stakeholder identification methodology, site coordinators were supported by pre-identified stakeholder groups to identify relevant parties at each site. Stakeholders were then mapped not only by their type but also by their level of influence and interest in the project.

Figure 6 illustrates the stakeholder mapping tool used in the project, which positions stakeholders according to two key parameters: **influence** and **interest**. This classification helps site coordinators and project partners strategically plan engagement approaches and understand the diverse roles stakeholders can play across experimental sites.

We implemented a process of influence and interest evaluation leveraging the site coordinator's knowledge in the region and expertise in similar topics related to land use activities. To complement this one-to-one meetings were organized to discuss the dimensions for evaluation as well as the regional dynamics.

Influence reflects a stakeholder's capacity to shape the outcomes of the project, as well as the broader social, political, economic, and environmental contexts surrounding each experimental site. To capture this complexity, the mapping tool distinguishes between four dimensions of influence:

- **Political influence**, such as authority over policy, land-use regulations, or institutional decisions affecting the site.
- **Economic influence**, including control over financial resources, employment, market access, or investment related to site activities.
- **Social influence**, which refers to the ability to mobilize communities, shape narratives, or foster cooperation and participation at the local level.
- **Environmental influence**, such as involvement in conservation, restoration, or land management practices with direct impact on soil and ecosystem health.

Each influence is scored using three levels: **low**, **medium**, and **high** influence. To provide a usable metric for analysis, the individual scores across the four influence dimensions are averaged into an overall influence level for each stakeholder.

Interest represents a stakeholder's willingness or motivation to engage with the project. Site coordinators were provided with dimensions of different forms of stakeholder interest to guide their evaluation:

- **Stay informed** about project developments
- **Interested** in sharing or gaining knowledge
- **Connect and network** with other stakeholders for collaboration
- **Contribute** expertise or co-develop solutions
- **Advocate** for particular values, such as biodiversity, sustainable farming, or economic resilience

Interest is also categorized on a **low–medium–high** scale, reflecting the intensity and scope of a stakeholder's engagement potential.

Fig.6: Stakeholder mapping matrix

By categorizing and visually mapping stakeholders according to these criteria, the project can efficiently engage the right stakeholders for various co-design and co-creation activities on diverse topics. This mapping allows us to target and involve stakeholders more effectively throughout the project.

Involve (high influence and low interest) = Stakeholders with high influence but not necessarily high interest in the project, should be kept updated and minimally engaged to secure their support in the project.

Collaborate (high influence and high interest) = stakeholders with both a high influence and interest are vital to the project's success and should be actively engaged and collaborated with.

Inform (low influence and low interest) = stakeholders with both a low influence and interest should be simply kept informed on any major project results to ensure our efforts and work are communicated and in the events the results will be deemed useful for these stakeholders.

Consult (low influence and high interest) = stakeholders with a low influence but high interest should still be actively engaged in the project to gather valuable insights and foster collaborative relationships.

5 Stakeholder identification and mapping per biogeographical region

This section outlines the stakeholders identification and mapping results for each experimental site. Identified stakeholders include both specific individuals and broader organizations or companies for which a contact person can be provided. To respect privacy, specific contact information is not included, instead the list and distribution of stakeholder categories is presented for each site. These stakeholder types were derived from the pre-identification process conducted during the initial desk research phase by LGI. The stakeholder categories are as follows:

- Civil society organisations
- Education, Research
- Finance & Business
- Media
- Public bodies
- Residents, Citizens
- Suppliers & Clients
- Workers & Farmers

The stakeholder mapping process involves organizing stakeholders based on their level of influence on the experimental site and their interest in participating in co-creation activities within the project. For each stakeholder map, key observations are highlighted to explain how the specific characteristics of the experimental site may contribute to the stakeholder's influence and interest.

The stakeholder identification and mapping are first conducted by biogeographical region and then by individual land use sites within each region. This approach provides both a high-level overview and a detailed site-specific analysis, enabling comparisons of outcomes across regions and land use types.

The following sections, organized by biogeographical region, present a detailed analysis of stakeholder identification and mapping for each region and its five experimental sites. Each section begins with an overview of the region, including its land use types and associated soil health pressures. A general stakeholder analysis is then provided for the region, followed by a more in-depth examination of stakeholder identification and mapping at the experimental site level. For each experimental site, a detailed description is included to highlight its characteristics, activities, and their relevance to stakeholder identification and mapping.

5.1. Alpine Experimental Sites

The 5 Alpine experimental sites are situated in Switzerland and consist of 5 different land-uses including agriculture, forest, industrial, semi-natural and wetland. This section provides an overview of the Alpine experimental sites.

Coordinator partner	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL)	
Experimental Site Name	Alpine Experimental Site	
Region	Grisons Graubünden	
Country	Switzerland	
Soil Pressures	Agricultural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soil fertility • Structure • Climate regulation
	Forest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss • Compaction • Erosion
	Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss • Contamination • Erosion
	Semi-natural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss • Compaction • Nutrient imbalance
	Wetland (Fen bog)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss • Red list species conservation

The Alpine region has a total of **48 identified stakeholders**. Figure 7 illustrates the distribution of these stakeholders across the five experimental sites. The majority of stakeholders fall into the *public bodies*, *workers and farmers*, and *suppliers & clients* categories. The distribution reflects the agricultural and tourism activities present at the Alpine sites. Suppliers, who provide necessary resources for agricultural activities, and clients, including those purchasing produce or engaging in tourism, also play vital roles. Public body stakeholders are integral to both local and regional communities and contribute by establishing regulations,

overseeing land use in the area and balancing agricultural production with environmental conservation and community interests.

Fig.7: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Alpine experimental sites

While the Alpine industrial and semi-natural experimental sites are the largest, spanning over 20 hectares, the agricultural site, which covers only about 500m², has the highest number of identified stakeholders. The agricultural site has 13 stakeholders, while the industrial and wetland sites each have 10 and 9 stakeholders, respectively. The higher number of stakeholders in the agricultural site can be attributed to the nature of agricultural activities, which require greater involvement from suppliers and clients. The next sections detail the stakeholder identification and mapping of the Alpine experimental sites.

The complete stakeholder list, distribution and mapping for the 5 Alpine sites are in [Annex 8.3.1](#).

5.2. Atlantic Experimental Sites

The 5 Atlantic experimental sites are situated in northern Spain and consist of 5 different land-uses including agriculture, mining, semi-natural, urban and wetland. This section provides an overview of the Atlantic experimental sites.

Coordinator partner	University of Vigo (Uvigo)	
Experimental Site Name	Atlantic Experimental Site	
Region	Galicia	
Country	Spain	
Soil Pressures	Agricultural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss • Compaction • Contamination
	Mining	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss • Organic matter loss • compaction • Contamination
	Semi natural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss • compaction
	Urban	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss • Compaction • Contamination • Soil sealing
	Wetland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss • Contamination

The Atlantic biogeographic region has a total of **105 identified stakeholders**, making it one of the regions with the highest number of stakeholders identified. This makes sense as all the sites in this region are relatively large, and include labour intensive activities including agriculture and mining. Specifically the agricultural (32 stakeholders) and urban (26 stakeholders) site have a high number of stakeholders. This can be explained due to the high

amount of workers including farmers, community gardeners and landscape companies needed at these sites.

Figure 8 illustrates the distribution of stakeholders and shows that the biggest stakeholder groups include *workers & farmers, public bodies, education & research institutions, and civil society organizations*.

Fig.8: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Atlantic experimental sites

Within the workers and farmers category, stakeholders primarily consist of farmers, site managers, mining companies, and landscaping firms. Given their direct involvement in site-related activities and their often local context, this group tends to have significant influence over the site's operations and overall context. However, the mapping of experimental sites reveals that while this stakeholder group wields considerable influence, their level of interest in the project tends to be lower compared to other stakeholders, such as research institutions.

The complete stakeholder list, distribution and mapping for the 5 Atlantic sites are in [Annex 8.3.2](#).

5.3. Boreal Experimental Sites

The 5 Boreal experimental sites are situated in Latvia and consist of 5 different land-uses including agriculture, forest, mining, semi-natural and wetland. This section provides an overview of the Boreal experimental sites.

Coordinator partner	Latvian State Forestry Research Institute (SILAVA)	
Experimental Site Name	Boreal Experimental Site	
Region	Central	
Country	Latvia	
Soil Pressures	Agricultural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutrient imbalance
	Forest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutrient imbalance • Acidification • Eutrophication
	Mining	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss • Erosion
	Semi natural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organic matter loss • Compaction
	Wetland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drainage • Organic matter loss • Habitat loss for wetland species

The Boreal region has a total of **194 identified stakeholders**, making it the region with the highest number of stakeholders. However, due to the overlap in environmental characteristics, since the forest, mining, semi-natural, and wetland sites all include forested areas, there is significant stakeholder overlap among these sites. The stakeholder lists for the forest, semi-natural, and wetland sites are nearly identical, differing by only one or two stakeholders. Additionally, stakeholder mapping remains similar, as the influence and interests of these stakeholders are consistent across different land-use sites.

Figure 9 illustrates the distribution of stakeholders, showing that the largest stakeholder groups include *educational and research institutions, public body institutions, and civil society organizations*. The analysis reveals a diverse and comprehensive distribution of stakeholders across the Boreal sites, making it the only region where all stakeholder categories are represented.

Fig.9: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Boreal experimental sites

Within the workers and farmers category, it is important to recognize that many of these stakeholders are also affiliated with public body institutions or governmental authorities. This is largely due to the fact that experimental sites in Latvia are often state-owned and managed. As a result, while site owners and managers are categorized as workers and farmers, they also hold official positions within public institutions, granting them significant decision-making authority and political influence over site management and land use policies.

Understanding this dual role is crucial because these stakeholders can valuably contribute to various co-creation activities covering topics from policy creation to land management and soil practices. These stakeholders can bridge the gap between policy design and real-world implementation, leading to more balanced, inclusive, and well-informed environmental and land management policies.

The complete stakeholder list, distribution and mapping for the 5 Boreal sites are in [Annex 8.3.3](#).

5.4. Continental Experimental Sites

The 5 Continental experimental sites are situated in Germany and consist of 5 different land-uses including agriculture, forest, mining, semi-natural and urban. This section provides an overview of the Continental experimental sites.

Coordinator partner	Thünen-Institute of Biodiversity (TI)	
Experimental Site Name	Continental Experimental Site	
Region	Rhineland	
Country	Germany	
Soil Pressures	Agricultural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss • Compaction • Erosion
	Forest	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss • Compaction • Organic matter loss
	Mining	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss • Organic matter loss • Contamination
	Semi natural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss • Surplus N-input • Organic matter loss
	Urban	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss • Pollution (plastic dispersal) • Soil sealing

There is a significant overlap amongst the continental sites, with many stakeholders participating in multiple locations. For example, each site includes 2 researchers from the Thünen Institute, which is the Continental site coordinator organisation, and 2 individuals responsible for coordinating and organizing experimental site activities. In total, **11 distinct stakeholders** are identified across this biogeographical region. The limited stakeholder diversity is particularly surprising given the substantial size and diverse

characteristics of the sites. The primary distinction between stakeholders across these sites lies in the site owners.

This biogeographical region has a more focused range of stakeholder types. While other regions engage stakeholders from a broader spectrum of categories, this site is represented by 4 key stakeholder categories, reflecting its specific context and priorities. Moreover, with the exception of the urban site, public bodies are absent from the stakeholder landscape across the sites. The process to identify and engage with public bodies will continue in order to answer to BIOServicES objectives.

Due to the similarities in stakeholder composition across the sites, the stakeholder maps also display consistent patterns. While overall stakeholders in this region reveal a generally low level of influence, they also show having quite high level of interest, which provides a valuable opportunity to engage effectively and foster strong collaborations.

Fig.10: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Continental experimental sites

The complete stakeholder list, distribution and mapping for the 5 Continental sites are in [Annex 8.3.4](#).

5.5. Mediterranean Experimental Sites

The 5 Mediterranean experimental sites are situated in Spain and consist of 5 different land-uses including agriculture, dryland, industry, mining and urban. This section provides an overview of the Mediterranean experimental sites.

Coordinator partner	Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC) AgroCultívate	
Experimental Site Name	Mediterranean Experimental Site	
Region	Aragon	
Country	Spain	
Soil Pressures	Agricultural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organic matter loss • Erosion • Soil structure & fertility loss
	Dryland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss • Organic matter loss • Erosion
	Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss • Erosion • Pollution drift
	Mining	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss • Organic matter loss • Erosion
	Urban	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biodiversity loss

The Mediterranean experimental site coordinators have identified a total of **25 stakeholders**, covering 6 stakeholder categories. The 3 largest categories include *workers & farmers*, *public body representatives*, and *education and research institutions*. The diversity in stakeholders allows us to incorporate different perspectives in co-creation activities for the Mediterranean experimental sites. It is noteworthy that no stakeholders from the civil society organization category have been identified in this region. This is surprising, as this category is represented in other biogeographical regions, where stakeholders such as nature conservation organizations play a critical

role in promoting soil health, as well as conserving nature and biodiversity. Through engagement strategies project partners can explore whether any civil society organisations are connected to the site.

Fig.11: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Mediterranean experimental sites

Public bodies represent key stakeholders, primarily consisting of local council and municipal representatives. These stakeholders typically exhibit the highest levels of both interest and influence, as their decision-making power directly impacts site operations and governance. On the other hand, farmers and workers, who play a key role in the operational activities of these sites, display varying levels of interest depending on the specific site and its activities.

The complete stakeholder list, distribution and mapping for the 5 Mediterranean sites are in [Annex 8.3.5](#).

5.6. Stakeholders identified across the 25 BIOServicES experimental sites

Tables 9 and 10 provide a comprehensive overview of stakeholder distribution across the project's biogeographical regions and land uses. In total 400 stakeholders are identified across the 25 BIOServicES experimental sites. Stakeholders are grouped into eight main categories, enabling a consistent identification while accommodating the site-specific variability in stakeholder roles, levels of influence and interest, and types of engagement. This section presents a synthesis of the stakeholders identified per category across 25 sites. Site-specific information is provided in Annex 8.3.

Civil society organisations include a wide range of actors involved in environmental advocacy, agricultural representation, public engagement, and community-based initiatives. These organisations often work to advance sustainability goals, supporting sustainable farming practices, promote biodiversity, and conservation. Some act as mediators between local populations and governing bodies, while others represent businesses, workers, hunters, and forest owners to represent their interest.

Education and research stakeholders represent one of the most active and extensive categories across all sites. This group comprises universities, national and regional research institutes, technical experts. They contribute knowledge in fields such as soil health, forestry, agroecology, environmental planning, and landscape restoration. Each site is also coordinated by a research institution, conducting field sampling. These stakeholders play a key role in connecting site-level practices to scientific frameworks.

Finance and business stakeholders engage in site-level activities through investment, service provision, and economic partnerships. They include private companies operating mainly within the tourism sector. Other stakeholders in this category provide financial support.

Media stakeholders are fewer in number but hold an important role in public communication and awareness-building. This group includes journalists, specialised magazines, local broadcasters, and thematic media outlets covering environmental, agricultural, and rural affairs.

Public bodies form one of the most structurally significant stakeholder groups. These stakeholders are part of local governments, municipal authorities, regional authorities, public organizations, and sectoral departments (including agriculture, climate and energy) dealing with land use, natural resources, groundwater protection, urban development, environmental protection, and rural policy. These stakeholders act as regulators (policy makers), funders and landowners, while also providing advisory services on agricultural matters, wetland and groundwater protection.

Residents and citizens contribute to the social context of the sites. These stakeholders include both informal users of the land (e.g. local residents, recreational visitors) and organised community and citizen associations. In some cases, these stakeholders use the land for leisure, gardening, or cultural activities, in others, they advocate for more sustainable or community-driven land use models. Stakeholders in this category are also a part of local resident's organizations advocating the interest of local farmers.

Suppliers and clients are actors who maintain the flow of goods, services into and out of the site. Suppliers include those providing agricultural inputs, forestry tools, training, or technical services. Clients include buyers of timber, livestock, and food products, as well as tourists who make use of ski and eco-tourism facilities at the sites. This category also includes stakeholders who lease the land for agricultural purposes or other farming-related activities.

Workers and farmers represent the group most directly involved in day-to-day site activities. This category includes farmers, ranchers, miners, foresters, landscapers, gardeners. These stakeholders are either individuals or part of a company, such as mining, landscaping or agriculture company who works on the land. These stakeholders implement direct land activities. In many cases, they are also the main stewards of the site, with direct decision-making responsibilities.

5.7. Stakeholder identification comparative analysis and key insights

The number of stakeholders varies considerably by region, which may be attributed to site-specific characteristics and the strength of direct relationships between stakeholder coordinators and the sites themselves. These differences highlight the influence of local contexts and engagement structures on stakeholder involvement.

A key finding from the tables is that the Education and research and Workers & Farmers categories constitutes the largest stakeholder group by a significant margin. Education and research institutions exhibit a strong presence across most land uses, with the notable exception of industrial sites. Their involvement is particularly valuable, as these institutions contribute expertise, facilitate knowledge exchange, and drive innovation in soil health and sustainable land management. Their high level of interest in BIOservicES aligns well with the project's overarching goal of advancing scientific research and developing evidence-based solutions for soil conservation and ecosystem services enhancement.

Stakeholders belonging to the Workers & Farmers category are directly involved in the operational aspects of the sites. The category encompasses a diverse range of professionals, including site managers, coordinators, farmers, landscaping professionals, industrial workers, miners, and gardeners. Notably, agricultural sites have the highest concentration of farmers, reflecting their essential role in agricultural activities and food production. Conversely, urban sites register the largest number of workers, primarily composed of employees from landscaping companies, gardening services, and other maintenance-related occupations.

Public bodies represent the third-largest stakeholder category, emphasizing their crucial oversight role across various land uses. These entities are instrumental in shaping policies and regulations that impact site management, resource allocation, and environmental conservation efforts. Importantly, this stakeholder group is consistently present across all land-use types, underscoring the universal role of government institutions in land governance.

Two unexpected observations emerged from the stakeholder data. First, there was a notable absence of civil society organizations at industrial sites. Given the significant environmental footprint of industrial activities, this highlights the need to explore whether targeted engagement could help identify relevant NGOs or nature conservation groups. Second, despite the critical role of the agricultural industry in soil health, its representation within BIOservicES appears limited at this stage, with only 15 stakeholders identified from the broader finance and business sector. As the stakeholder identification remains a living process, this will be a continued action where

close collaboration with site coordinators and stakeholder networks will be key to identify and invite agro-industry actors. Strengthening this engagement will be essential to ensure that BIOservicES can meaningfully contribute to the overarching objectives of the EU SOILMISSION program.

Agricultural together with mining and semi-natural land use sites stand out as the most stakeholder-diverse environments. This diversity is expected, given the multifaceted nature of agricultural and mining operations. These sites necessitate a substantial workforce, engage with suppliers for inputs such as seeds, fertilizers, and machinery, maintain commercial relationships with buyers and distributors, collaborate with research institutions for technological advancements, and adhere to regulatory frameworks set by local and regional authorities.

In contrast, the dryland site has the lowest number of stakeholders. This is largely attributable to the fact that only one such site is included in the study, combined with the environmental constraints of drylands, which typically lead to lower productivity and limited human activity.

Urban and semi-natural sites also exhibit high levels of stakeholder engagement, reflecting their diverse and dynamic ecosystems. Urban sites, beyond the prevalence of community gardeners and landscaping professionals, also feature significant involvement from residents, who are identified as key stakeholders due to their direct interaction with and dependence on the urban environment. Semi-natural landscapes, while varying in characteristics across regions, often maintain some level of agricultural productivity, further reinforcing the role of farmers.

Overall, the stakeholder distribution patterns observed in this study provide critical insights into the social and economic networks underpinning different land uses. These findings will help shape future stakeholder engagement strategies, ensuring that all relevant actors are adequately represented and actively contribute to the co-creation activities. Furthermore, the understanding of stakeholder interest and influence distribution across sites will greatly enhance our ability to include the right stakeholders in engagement activities. By engaging the most relevant actors in collaborative efforts, partners can develop more effective and context-specific solutions for soil conservation and land management.

Comparative analysis stakeholder categories per biogeographical region

		Biogeographical Region					Total
		Alpine	Atlantic	Boreal	Continental	Mediterranean	
Stakeholder Category	Civil Society Organisations	3	12	28	3		46
	Education, Research	2	13	75	10	4	104
	Finance & Business	2	6	7			15
	Media		3	22		1	26
	Public bodies	15	24	33	1	5	78
	Residents, Citizens	4		4		3	11
	Suppliers & Clients	11	4	3		1	19
	Workers & Farmers	11	43	22	14	11	101
	Total	48	105	194	28	25	400

Table 9: Comparative analysis stakeholder categories per biogeographical region

Comparative analysis stakeholder categories per land use

		Land Use								
		Agricultural (5 sites)	Dryland (1 site)	Forest (3 sites)	Industrial (3 sites)	Mining (3 sites)	Semi-natural (4 sites)	Urban (3 sites)	Wetland (3 sites)	Total
Stakeholder Category	Civil Society Organisations	8		7		6	9	8	8	46
	Education, Research	17	1	19		19	22	21	3	102
	Finance & Business	3			2	5	4		1	15
	Media	5		5		5	5	6		26
	Public bodies	15	1	11	3	11	12	13	12	78
	Residents, Citizens	3	1	1		1	2	3		11
	Suppliers & Clients	13			5	1	2			21
	Workers & Farmers	22	1	10	6	15	17	25	5	101
	Total	86	4	53	16	63	73	76	29	400

Table 10: Comparative analysis stakeholder categories per land use

6 Stakeholder engagement and co-creation activities

The stakeholder identification and mapping activities under T1.1 are a critical step in ensuring the successful development and implementation of co-creation, co-innovation, and co-learning activities. This process enables us to identify which stakeholders to engage in specific activities that align with their interests. Furthermore, by understanding their interests and influence, partners can design tailored co-creation activities that not only capture relevant information but also provide stakeholders with valuable insights, tools, and resources.

The BIOServicES grant agreement clearly outlines the co-creation activities planned throughout the project. These activities will be co-organized by LGI in collaboration with WP leaders, who will define the content and objectives of each activity and session.

The activities include a clear timeline and description:

- M5: Agreement on selection and use of soil indicators for WP2. One full-day hybrid workshop, physically at least for WP2 partners, EEA, JRC and GSP. All biodiversity experts and land managers in each experimental site will be engaged, together with EU and International initiatives. A list of indicators will be forwarded before the workshop to prepare the discussion.
- M6: Agreement on soil sampling, sample pre-treatment, storage and shipment for WP2. One full-day online workshop for WP2 partners, EEA, JRC, GSP, biodiversity experts and land managers in each experimental site and EU and international initiatives.
- M8: Agreement on procedures and methods for soil analyses for WP2. One full-day hybrid workshop, physically at least for WP2 partners, EEA, JRC and GSP. All biodiversity experts and land managers in each experimental site will be engaged, together with EU and International initiatives.
- M8: Agreement on economic indicators to value soil ES for WP4. Online full-day workshop with WP4 partners, EEA, JRC and GSP, environment and economic experts in each experimental site and EU and International initiatives.
- M14 to M60: two hybrid workshops per year for a continuous exchange in each biogeographic region, chaired by LGI in collaboration with the experimental site leaders. Objectives:
 - Farmers, certification specialists, and policy makers will be engaged to co-build on existing carbon farming certification by adding new quality indicators and new rules for certification to propose to stakeholders an

improvement of existing certification scheme to value the soil biodiversity (WP5).

- Farmers, foresters, industries, mining, entrepreneurs, investors, consumers, policy makers (tax incentives/barriers), public authorities, will be invited in order to test payment scheme (pricing and business tools) and local policy (WP5).
- Farmers, foresters, industries, mining, entrepreneurs, investors, policy makers, public authorities, scientists will be invited in order to test and challenge the economic outcomes developed in WP4.
- M30 to M50: Assist task 3.3 to evaluate the SMART indicators through a fuzzy expert system, with engagement of JRC and EEA. At least three online meetings will be organized with experts in soil indicators, soil biodiversity and ES, linked to each experimental site and EU and international initiatives.
- M47: Assist task 2.7 for the ex-post evaluation of agreed methods and WP4 outputs. One full-day hybrid workshop, physically at least for WP2 and WP4 partners, EEA, JRC and GSP. All biodiversity, environmental and economic experts and land managers in each experimental site will be engaged, together with EU and International initiatives.
- M48 to M60: four online workshops with EU and international initiatives, public authorities and EC to discuss the elaboration of an international treaty for soil exchange and transfer activities, including sharing research facilities. JRC and EEA will have a key role within this activity. This will materialized in a Working Report on International Treaty for Soil Exchange, addressed to public authorities, included within D1.4.

The sessions in T3.1 will involve the relevant stakeholders identified and mapped during this task. Additionally, stakeholders may be invited to participate in activities conducted under other work packages if these activities offer value to the stakeholders and enable partners to gather valuable insights and results from experts associated with the sites.

6.1. Stakeholder engagement and collaboration tools

The BIOServicES project aims to leverage diverse tools and strategies to facilitate the organization of co-creation activities and enhance high-level stakeholder engagement throughout the project. A key resource supporting these efforts is the collaborative platform developed under T1.4. This platform plays a critical role in broadening the project's outreach, enabling seamless communication and collaboration with external stakeholders beyond the project partners.

This collaborative platform, jointly funded by the InBestSoil and BIOservicES projects, is known as the Soil Community Platform. The name was intentionally chosen to extend the platform's relevance and accessibility, transforming it into a resource that can be utilized by a wide range of projects and initiatives focused on soil health. This broad scope aims to create a hub for knowledge-sharing and engagement across different networks and stakeholders, fostering a larger community of practitioners.

The Soil Community Platform offers the flexibility to host a variety of public and private co-creation activities, such as webinars, workshops, and interactive sessions. These activities provide stakeholders with opportunities to connect, exchange knowledge, and collaborate on solutions to soil health challenges.

To support focused discussions and co-creation activities related to specific work packages and themes, the platform features dedicated groups, each tailored to key topics:

- Communication & Networking
- Economic Valuation of Soil Health
- Living Labs and Light Houses
- Policies on Soil Health
- Soil Health Indicators, Analysis, and Monitoring
- Events & Meetings

These groups foster in-depth, topic-specific discussions and encourage engagement among stakeholders with expertise or interest in the respective areas. By organizing conversations around these themes, the platform enables more targeted collaboration and knowledge exchange, ultimately advancing progress on soil health solutions.

6.2. Limitations & strategies to implement the co-creation activities

In the context of soil health projects, various stakeholder engagement barriers and challenges can arise. We discuss them in this section and highlight **Strategies** to overcome them.

Firstly, local stakeholders, particularly farmers, may **be less inclined to use online tools or digital platforms**, which can make it difficult to engage them effectively through virtual platforms like the Soil Community Platform. As such, it's crucial to consider **non-virtual co-creation activities** and organize **in-person events** and sessions to ensure their participation.

Moreover, many of the identified stakeholders are external to the project and do not work directly with the experimental site coordinators. As a result, they may be focused on their own more immediate priorities, having **limited time and resources to engage in project activities**. It is vital for the project to recognize these constraints and engage stakeholders in a meaningful and sustainable way. This includes **aligning activities with their interests and needs, offering flexible meeting times, and providing sufficient notice** so stakeholders can plan and organize their participation effectively.

Given the international scope of BIOservicES and its presence across multiple biogeographical regions, another challenge is the **potential language barrier**, as some stakeholders may not be comfortable communicating in English. To overcome this, the project should **provide resources in local languages** or ensure that partners are available to **facilitate communication between English and local languages. Multilingual support** for materials, meetings, and platforms is essential to ensure inclusivity.

An additional challenge involves avoiding the **overburdening of stakeholders** with multiple co-creation activities. Partners should organize these activities thoughtfully, ensuring that stakeholders are not contacted too frequently. Instead, **combining activities** where possible can help minimize the time commitment for stakeholders, making their involvement more manageable and sustainable.

Finally, while stakeholder engagement may be successful, demonstrating tangible outcomes and valuable results, such as improved soil health or policy changes, can be complex and may not be immediate. The **absence of quick, visible results** could lead to disengagement, which makes it crucial for partners **to set clear, measurable goals and communicate these effectively to stakeholders**. By doing so, the project can maintain long-term engagement and ensure that stakeholders remain invested in the process.

7 Conclusion

The stakeholder identification and mapping exercise is a crucial step in gaining a deeper understanding of the experimental site's characteristics and the role of different stakeholder groups. This process directly contributes to strengthening subsequent tasks and work packages that rely on meaningful engagement and interaction with the identified stakeholders. Through co-creation and co-learning activities, stakeholder engagement can be expanded, fostering new connections and further refining the initial stakeholder identification and mapping process.

Stakeholder engagement remains a fundamental aspect of soil health projects funded by the European Commission. The Soil Deal for Europe dedicates a specific cluster to effectively engaging diverse stakeholder groups to improve soil health. The methodology applied in this report aims to create a more standardized and robust approach to stakeholder identification and mapping across different projects. The pre-identification of stakeholders based on land use characteristics serves as a valuable tool for categorizing and referencing stakeholders within specific groups, facilitating a more structured engagement process.

By mapping stakeholders' interests and influence, we can strategically determine the level of engagement required for each group. This approach allows us to identify which stakeholders should be kept informed (low interest and influence), involved (low interest but high influence), consulted (high interest but low influence), or actively collaborated with (high interest and influence). This structured understanding enables more effective interaction and ensures that engagement efforts are targeted and impactful.

The stakeholder identification and mapping process revealed significant variations in stakeholder presence across different sites, highlighting the diverse roles and priorities associated with different land uses. While this process aids in facilitating engagement, it remains a complex task, with various challenges and barriers to consider. Given the often localized nature of stakeholders, it is essential to communicate with them in their native languages and provide accessible tools or resources to support interactions between project partners and stakeholders. Furthermore, considering the high number of co-creation activities planned, it is crucial to avoid overburdening stakeholders. Engagement efforts should be carefully coordinated to ensure that participation remains manageable and valuable for stakeholders. Most importantly, activities should provide direct benefits to stakeholders, reinforcing their motivation to engage. Understanding stakeholders' interests and influence helps determine the extent and manner of their inclusion, ensuring that their participation aligns with both project objectives and their own priorities and that the project can maintain long-term engagement and ensure that stakeholders remain invested in the process.

8 Annex

8.1.High-level overview Experimental Sites

Region (country)	Land Use	Main Pressures	Soil Type	Vegetation	Partner
Alpine (Switzerland)	Industrial	Contamination, Compaction	Technosol	Pasture	FiBL / ANU
	Agricultural	Biodiversity loss, OM loss	Regosol	Pasture	
	Forest	Biodiversity loss, OM loss	Cambisol	Mixed	
	Semi-natural	Biodiversity loss, erosion	Regosol	Meadow	
	Wetland	OM loss	Histosol	Meadow	
Atlantic (Spain)	Urban	Biodiversity loss	Regosol	Grasses	UVigo / FJV
	Agricultural	Biodiversity loss, compaction	Umbrisol	Vineyards	
	Mining	Biodiversity loss, OM loss	Technosol	Pinus sp.	
	Semi-natural	Biodiversity loss	Umbrisol	Quercus sp.	
	Wetland	Biodiversity loss	Fluvisol	Riparian	
Boreal (Latvia)	Agricultural	Nutrient imbalance	Histosol	Orchard	SILAVA / RM
	Forest	Acidification	Histosol	Mixed	
	Mining	Biodiversity loss, erosion	Histosol	Bare / pines	
	Semi-natural	OM loss, compaction	Histosol	Mixed	
	Wetland	Nutr. Imbalance, acidification	Histosol	Typha sp	
Continental (Germany)	Urban	Biodiversity loss, soil sealing, pollution	Technosol	Grasses	TI / FAR
	Mining	Biodiversity loss, OM loss, contamination	Technosol	Shrubs / Trees	
	Agricultural	Biodiversity loss, compaction, erosion	Cambisol	Arable crops	
	Forest	Biodiversity loss, compaction, OM loss	Cambisol	Trees	
	Semi-natural	Biodiversity loss, surplus N-input, OM loss	Cambisol	/ Grasses	
Mediterranean (Spain)	Urban	Biodiversity loss	Calcisol	Ornamental	CSIC / SAC
	Industrial	Biodiversity loss, erosion	Calcisol	Shrubs	
	Agricultural	OM loss, erosion	Calcisol	Cereals	
	Mining	OM loss, desertification	Technosol	Shrubs	
	Dryland	OM loss, desertification	Calcisol	Shrubs	

OM = Organic matter

Nutr. = Nutrient

Biodiv. = Biodiversity

8.2. Stakeholder Identification Template

N° of stakeholder /cat	STEP 1 & 2 : STAKEHOLDER IDENTIFICATION					STEP 3 : STAKEHOLDER CLASIFICATION		
	Select type of stakeholder	Organization name	Organization's Main contact Full Name	Main contact (Email or phone number)	Other contacts (Email or phone number)	Description of stakeholder actions (what does this stakeholder do?)	Is the stakeholder Internal/External to the experimental site	Is the stakeholder working on local, regional, national or european level?
1								
2								
3								
4								

STEP 4 : LEVEL OF INFLUENCE AND INTEREST							STEP 5&6 : CO-CREATION ACTIVITIES		
What type of influence does this stakeholder have on the project	How much ECONOMIC influence does this stakeholder exert on the Experimental site activities?	How much SOCIAL influence does this stakeholder exert on the Experimental site activities?	How much ENVIRONMENT influence does this stakeholder exert on the Experimental site activities?	How much POLITICAL influence does this stakeholder exert on the Experimental site	What potential interest does this stakeholder have on the project	What Level of interest does this stakeholder have on the project (high, medium, low)	If possible, please describe the interest	If possible, identify co-creation activities to involve stakeholder in	Additional comments on the stakeholder

8.3. Stakeholder Identification and mapping per site

This annex presents the stakeholder identification and mapping for each site. Stakeholders are identified based on their type and category. Due to GDPR compliance, no contact information, including name, email, organization is provided.

8.1.1 Stakeholder identification and mapping Alpine sites

Agricultural Land use: stakeholder identification

Table 11 summarises the characteristics of the Alpine agricultural land use site.

Alpine agricultural land use site

Agricultural Land Use: Crops on farm experiments at Plantahof Mission Soil: impact of production intensity	
Extension	500 m ²
Description geographical context	The soils in the Rhine valley are primarily used for agriculture and have a characteristic black colour, derived from the geological material they are formed from. The texture is predominantly loamy.
Soil Health Pressures	Soil fertility, Structure & Climate regulation
Soil Health Practices	Soil optimization management
Intensity 1	Integrated production, manure, no tillage for 15 years, ÖLN
Intensity 2	Integrated production, manure, plough, part of Climate Farmers program, ÖLN
Intensity 3	Crop rotation with strawberry and raspberry production highly intense, use of peat

Table 11: Alpine agricultural land use site

The agricultural land use site has a total of 13 stakeholders identified.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Cantonal advisory service, applied research
Farmers and agricultural producers (livestock owners included)	Workers & Farmers	Berry production
Direct clients (cooperatives, farmers organizations...)	Suppliers & Clients	IP Sekretariat Graubünden
Direct clients (cooperatives, farmers organizations...)	Suppliers & Clients	Not known
Rural Communities and Residents organizations	Residents, citizens	Also delegates of Bio Suisse listed under this link
Local residents' associations	Residents, citizens	support of regional projects aiming at net zero
Local residents' associations	Residents, citizens	Association and exchange platform about direct sowing
Indirect clients (retailers, consumers...)	Suppliers & Clients	Buy and sell regional food
Indirect clients (retailers, consumers...)	Suppliers & Clients	Buy and sell regional food
Suppliers and subcontractors (i.e. agricultural inputs, seeds, fertilizers, equipment...)	Suppliers & Clients	Buy regional products
Indirect clients (retailers, consumers...)	Suppliers & Clients	Consumption of regional products
Academics in agricultural, environmental science and economics	Education, Research	Research Institute for Organic Agriculture (FiBL)
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Officer for groundwater protection and use

Table 12: Stakeholder identification Alpine agricultural land use site

Figure 12 shows the distribution of stakeholder groups in this site.

Fig.12: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Alpine agricultural land use site

Education, Research: The research organisation identified is the experimental site coordinator of the Alpine region experimental sites, the Research Institute for Organic Agriculture (FiBL). FiBL has direct ties to the site and is conducting its soil sampling activities in this region.

Public bodies: Two public bodies were identified, both operating at the regional level. One provides guidance and advisory services, while the other is responsible for groundwater protection.

Residents, Citizens: Three local residents' associations/communities have been identified, each focused on improving specific practices within agricultural environments. One is dedicated to reducing tillage, another aims to achieve climate-neutral agriculture, and the third works to promote organic farming practices and support organic producers.

Suppliers & Clients: Suppliers and clients are by far the largest group for this site, due to the agriculture activities that take place. These activities create a significant demand for suppliers of machinery and equipment, as well as clients who purchase and distribute the locally produced food.

Workers & Farmers: Only one farming organization has been identified, which is directly involved in working the land and contributing to agricultural food production.

Agricultural Land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 13 maps the stakeholder categories across their interest and influence in the project.

Fig.13: Stakeholder mapping Alpine agricultural land use site

In this agricultural experimental site, there is an overall high interest and influence of stakeholders, making stakeholder collaboration and engagement crucial for this experimental site. Specifically, the public authority and farming stakeholders have a significant influence on the site. The local farmer is primarily responsible for agricultural production and land management, exerting significant influence over the site's economic, social, and environmental dimensions. In contrast, public regulatory bodies play a key role in shaping the site's political landscape, exercising decision-making authority over regional land management, water resource regulation, and the enforcement of policies that support sustainable agricultural practices and environmental conservation. The Plantahof is one of these public bodies, serving as the regional hub for advisory services and a liaison for policy matters. Simultaneously, it functions as an agricultural vocational school engaged in applied research. As a result, its role in the project may be twofold, and we must remain mindful of this dual responsibility.

Another interesting observation is that while the suppliers and clients constitute the largest stakeholder category at this site, they demonstrate the lowest levels of interest on the project. Despite their limited interest, their vital role in the site's operations means it is crucial to keep them informed about the project activities and its outcomes.

The research institution FiBL stands out for its high interest in the project, as their expertise on organic agricultural production and farming can bring interesting insights to the project.

Forest land use: stakeholder identification

Table 13 summarises the characteristics of the Alpine forest land use site.

Alpine forest land use site

Forest Land Use: Forest-pasture Mission Soil: competing use as meadow and forest	
Extension	500 m ²
Description geographical context	The forest on the steep slopes above the village of Trin serves an important protective function (Schutzwald), safeguarding the inhabited areas below. The soils are primarily composed of granite gravel which are vulnerable to erosion and compaction due to grazing activities. Scattered throughout the landscape are ancient larch trees and the denser forest is dominated by coniferous vegetation.
Soil Health Pressures	Biodiversity loss & compaction
Soil Health Practices	Afforestation and/or natural rejuvenation
Intensity 1	No trees in a radius of 5 m (degraded forest) and undercover vegetation
Intensity 2	1-3 trees in a radius of 5 m (More trees) but still a good understory vegetation
Intensity 3	More than 3 trees in a radius of 5 m (dense stand of coniferous trees) and poor understory vegetation

Table 13: Alpine forest land use site

The forest land use site has a total of seven stakeholders identified, distributed across the public entities and workers & farmers categories.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	President of the community Trin
Farmers and agricultural producers (livestock owners included)	Workers & Farmers	Not known
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Responsible for soil protection
Farmers and agricultural producers (livestock owners included)	Workers & Farmers	Not known
Farmers and agricultural producers (livestock owners included)	Workers & Farmers	Not known
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Cantonal advisory service, applied research
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Natural risk management

Table 14: Stakeholder identification Alpine forest land use site

Figure 14 illustrates the distribution of stakeholder groups within this site.

Fig.14: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Alpine forest land use site

Public bodies: A total of four public bodies have been identified as stakeholders for the forest experimental site in the Alpine region. These

include stakeholders representing the local community and public organizations involved in regional advisory services and risk management.

Workers & Farmers: This group comprises three local farmers who actively work on the experimental site, making them key stakeholders in the project.

Forest Land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 15 maps the stakeholder categories across their interest and influence in the project.

Fig.15: Stakeholder mapping Alpine forest land use site

Overall, limited information was available regarding the influence and interest of the local farmers, leading to their placement in the middle of the stakeholder map. However, given their local context and direct connection to the forest, the farmers likely have a significant environmental influence on site activities. Therefore, it is essential to engage with this stakeholder group and leverage their expertise in any forest-related activities during the project, as these are likely the activities that align most closely with their interests.

The municipal and regulatory authorities associated with the site were identified as having a high level of interest in the project, alongside a medium to high degree of influence over site activities. These stakeholders predominantly impact the political and environmental context of the site.

Industrial land use: stakeholder identification

Table 15 summarises the characteristics of the Alpine industrial land use site.

Alpine industrial land use site

Industrial Land Use: Skiing run & lift Mission Soil: protect the landscape, alternative uses	
Extension	20 ha
Description geographical context	Alpine meadows are extensively used for summer grazing and often serve as ski slopes in winter. The landscape and soils exhibit signs of terrain modification for ski runs, as well as the trampling impact of cattle. In summer, the area also serves as a popular hiking destination. Ski runs are covered with artificial snow, which is flattened during the early morning hours.
Soil Health Pressures	Tourism and grazing causing Biodiversity loss, Contamination & Erosion
Soil Health Practices	No specific soil health practices
Intensity 1	Modified terrain, crossing of several runways, intense artificial snow, summer grazing
Intensity 2	Skiing runway, no artificial snow, no terrain change
Intensity 3	Semi-natural vegetation, shrubland, no skiing, grazing allowed

Table 15: Alpine industrial land use site

The Alpine industrial experimental site has a total of 10 stakeholders identified.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Responsible for plantahof farm unit, that is managing part of the skiing and summer grazing land
Transport and logistics companies	Suppliers & Clients	Sustain and run lifts, maintain infrastructure for transport
Industry Associations	Workers & Farmers	Marketing and offering touristic attractions
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Communal authorities
Farmers and agricultural producers (livestock owners included)	Workers & Farmers	Farmers grazing their cows in summer in the tourist area
Direct clients	Suppliers & Clients	Recreation activities
Direct clients (cooperatives, farmers organizations...)	Suppliers & Clients	Provision of snow, infrastructure
Eco or nature tourism	Finance & Business	Administration of touristic offers
Workers, former workers	Workers & Farmers	Seasonal worker
Eco or nature tourism	Finance & Business	Administration of touristic offers

Table 16: Stakeholder identification Alpine industrial land use site

Figure 16 shows the distribution of stakeholder groups in this site.

Fig.16: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Alpine industrial land use site

Finance & Business: Due to the site's ski resort and eco-tourism activities, two tourism-related stakeholders have been identified. These stakeholders contribute to the region's economy by providing regional and local tourism facilities, generating income for the area.

Public bodies: Two public bodies are also connected to the site, including local municipal authorities responsible for overseeing and authorizing ski resort operations.

Suppliers & Clients: The 3 Suppliers and clients, include one transport and logistic company providing the ski lifts for the site and snow-making machines. Direct clients consist of tourists who visit to enjoy the ski resort and local attractions.

Workers & Farmers: Three key stakeholders have been identified, including employees working in the ski area, such as those in tourist offices, as well as farmers managing the land and overseeing cattle farming.

Industrial Land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 17 maps the stakeholders of the industrial experimental site across their interest and influence in the project.

Fig.17: Stakeholder mapping Alpine industrial land use site

Limited information is available about the interest levels of the stakeholders of this site, leading to most stakeholder groups being mapped at a moderate level of interest. However, the influence of stakeholders is more clearly defined. Regulatory bodies show to have lower influence on the industrial site compared to the forest and agricultural sites. Through the stakeholder engagement activities we can continue to observe their influence over the various Alpine sites.

The remaining three stakeholder groups show relatively higher levels of influence on the industrial site. Suppliers and clients have the greatest influence on the site's environmental and economic context, as they provide the essential infrastructure for the ski resort. Worker stakeholders and tourism businesses, who actively ensure the resort's operation, have the most significant impact on the site's economic success.

More research will be conducted to know how the different type of stakeholders would like to be included in the project's co-creation activities.

Semi-natural land use: stakeholder identification

Table 17 summarises the characteristics of the Alpine semi-natural land use site.

Alpine semi-natural land use site

Semi-natural Land Use: Milk & meat production Mission Soil: competing use as meadow and forest	
Extension	20 ha
Description geographical context	The Trin area is characterized by soils primarily under permanent grassland, developed on limestone and marl from historic rockfalls. Soil thickness varies significantly, ranging from 20 to 120 cm. The top 5-10 cm exhibit mollic SOM accumulation and acidic topsoil. Below this layer, weak indications of podzolization are present, followed by virgin limestone.
Soil Health Pressures	Biodiversity loss, compaction & nutrient imbalance
Soil Health Practices	No specific soil health practices
Intensity 1	5 cuts per year, manure and slurry use, high input, ÖLN
Intensity 2	2-3 cuts per year, only farmyard manure use once a year
Intensity 3	1 cut per year, no fertilizer

Table 17: Alpine semi-natural land use site

The semi-natural land use site has 9 stakeholders identified across various stakeholder categories.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Site responsible Owners and managers of the agricultural site	Workers & Farmers	Suckler cow husbandry
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Cantonal advisory service, applied research
Environmental and Conservation Organizations (environmental impacts of Agri practices and could advocate for sustainable and ecofriendly farming..)	Civil society organisations	Not known
Site responsible Owners and managers of the agricultural site	Workers & Farmers	Sheep farming
Direct clients (cooperatives, farmers organizations...)	Suppliers & Clients	Buyer of local products
Suppliers and subcontractors (i.e. agricultural inputs, seeds, fertilizers, equipment...)	Suppliers & Clients	Provide agricultural inputs
Rural Communities and Residents organizations	Residents, Citizens	Protects interests of cantonal agriculture
NGO on agricultural or rural development	Civil society organisations	Not known
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Officer for groundwater protection

Table 18: Stakeholder identification Alpine semi-natural land use site

Figure 18 illustrates the distribution of stakeholder groups within this site.

Fig.18: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Alpine semi-natural land use site

Civil society organisations: Two associations connected to this site are dedicated to agricultural development and promoting environmentally sustainable farming practices.

Public bodies: Two public bodies were identified, both operating at the regional level. One provides guidance and advisory services, while the other is responsible for groundwater protection.

Residents, Citizens: One local residents' organization is connected to the site, advocating for the interests of farmers and supporting agricultural development in the region.

Suppliers & Clients: Given the production of local products at this site, one client group has been identified as local farmers who purchase these products. Additionally, a supplier stakeholder has been identified, providing fertilizers, machinery, and other agricultural supplies essential for operations.

Workers & Farmers: Two site managers have been identified, both categorized under the farming & worker group, as they are directly responsible for overseeing the site. One stakeholder manages cattle farming, while the other is responsible for sheep farming.

Semi-natural land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 19 maps the stakeholders of the semi-natural experimental site across their interest and influence in the project.

Fig.19: Stakeholder mapping Alpine semi-natural land use site

Among the stakeholder groups identified for this site, public authorities and farmers/workers exhibit the highest level of interest. Given the site's focus on agricultural production, site managers, who oversee cattle and sheep farming, play a crucial role. These local stakeholders are essential for maintaining agricultural operations and strengthening relationships with suppliers and clients. Actively engaging them in co-creation activities will provide valuable insights into their role in enhancing soil health management and practices.

However, compared to other experimental sites, the overall influence of stakeholders here is notably lower, with most demonstrating low to medium levels of influence. Among the groups, the site managers stand out for their significant impact on environmental and social aspects. Their decision-making authority over site practices, combined with their ability to engage with other stakeholders, makes them essential participants in discussions on soil health management.

Civil society organizations also play an important role, particularly in influencing the environmental aspects of the site. Their focus on conservation and sustainability aligns closely with the project's objective.

Wetland land use: stakeholder identification

Table 19 summarises the characteristics of the Alpine wetland land use site.

Alpine wetland land use site

Wetland Land Use: Nature protection site Mission Soil: conflict of agriculture and nature protection	
Extension	0.5 ha
Description geographical context	Weihermühle is an artificial fen bog developed from a pond that was created hundreds of years ago. The waterflooded site is home to a wide variety of amphibians. Nutrients arriving at the fen bog over water streams from higher areas are boosting the biomass.
Soil Health Pressures	Biodiversity loss and conservation of Red List species are key concerns. The drier areas are fertilized grasslands for fodder, and combined with nutrient runoff from creeks feeding into the fen, this may reduce biodiversity in the bog.
Soil Health Practices	Biomass removal in the flooded areas is carried out to reduce nutrient loads. The fen bog is under natural protection and supervised by a nature protection agency.
Intensity 1	Slurry fertilized grassland - no flooding
Intensity 2	Temporarily flooded
Intensity 3	Permanently flooded

Table 19: Alpine wetland land use site

The wetland land use site has a total of 9 stakeholders identified.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Responsible for soil protection
NGO on conservation	Civil society organisation	Land owner & coordinator of protected land because of its importance for biodiversity and rare species. They have contract with farmers to use the agricultural parts of the land.
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Head of the administration of the commune Bonaduz
Farmers and agricultural producers (livestock owners included)	Workers & Farmers	Management of meadows close to wet land area
Farmers and agricultural producers (livestock owners included)	Workers & Farmers	Not known
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Cantonal advisory service, applied research
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Responsible of Wetland protection
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Officer for groundwater protection
Academics in agricultural, environmental science and economics	Education, Research	Expert on agriculture and wetland protection

Table 20: Stakeholder identification Alpine wetland land use site

Figure 20 shows the distribution of stakeholder groups in this site.

Fig.20: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Alpine wetland land use site

Civil society organisations: One NGO has been identified, which is responsible for coordinating the management of biodiversity and species within the protected lands of the area.

Education, Research: One agricultural research centre has been identified, specializing in wetland protection and staffed with experts in the field.

Public bodies: Four regional public stakeholders have been identified, offering advisory services as well as expertise in wetland and groundwater protection.

Workers & Farmers: Two local farmers have been identified, responsible for managing the meadows adjacent to the wetland area.

Wetland land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 21 maps the stakeholder groups of the wetland experimental site across their interest and influence in the project.

Fig.21: Stakeholder mapping Alpine wetland land use site

Stakeholders of the Alpine wetland experimental site demonstrate a high level of interest in the project, making their engagement in co-creation activities crucial. Among them, the NGO focused on land conservation and protection, categorized as a civil society organization, stands out for its significant interest and influence. This stakeholder plays a central role in managing and coordinating the site, holding substantial influence over its economic, environmental, and political contexts. Their responsibilities include deciding on land-use practices and managing contracts with farmers who utilize the agricultural sections of the wetland.

In contrast, the research institution involved has a comparatively lower level of influence, as they are not directly engaged in land management or decision-making. Their primary contribution lies in providing valuable expertise on wetland protection and agriculture, supporting the site through knowledge rather than governance.

8.1.2 Stakeholder identification and mapping Atlantic sites

Agricultural land use: stakeholder identification

Table 21 summarises the characteristics of the Atlantic agricultural land use site.

Atlantic agricultural land use site

Agricultural Land Use: Vinyards Mission Soil: Reduction of management intensity	
Extension	3 ha
Description geographical context	The agricultural areas are situated in the O Ribeiro region, a prominent wine district in Galicia known for its white wines. This region is defined by small to medium-sized vineyards that vary in management practices and scale. The studied vineyards have been consistently managed under the same system for almost 15 years.
Soil Health Pressures	Biodiversity loss, compaction, soil contamination.
Soil Health Practices	Reduction of plant protection products application with cover crops and soil optimization management
Intensity 1	Herbicides, fungicides and mechanical vegetation clearing
Intensity 2	Herbicides on wine rows fungicides and mechanical vegetation clearing
Intensity 3	Agroecological weed management (cover crops)

Table 21: Atlantic agricultural land use site

The Atlantic agricultural land use site has the highest number of stakeholder identification, with a total of 32 stakeholders identified.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Suppliers and subcontractors (i.e. agricultural inputs, seeds, fertilizers, equipment...)	Suppliers & Clients	Organic fertilizer company
Research organisms	Education, Research	Investigating centre focused on land studies
Agriculture newspapers	Media	Online newspaper
Soil experts	Education, Research	Technic soils company
Suppliers and subcontractors (i.e. agricultural inputs, seeds, fertilizers, equipment...)	Suppliers & Clients	Fertilizer industry based on circular economy
Direct clients (cooperatives, farmers organizations...)	Suppliers & Clients	Ecological rancher cooperative. Native breeds. Extensive management
Farmers and agricultural producers (livestock owners included)	Workers & Farmers	Ecological ranchers. Native breeds. Extensive management
Research organisms	Education, Research	Research centre focused on agriculture investigations
Research organisms	Education, Research	Researchers working in solutions for plant illnesses and plagues
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Institution linked to the regional government aimed to advise in agricultural matters
Labor Unions and syndicate	Workers & Farmers	Rural advisers association
Soil experts	Education, Research	Expert in ecological management of the land for rancher purposes
Farmers and agricultural producers (livestock owners included)	Workers & Farmers	Syntropic agriculture station
Direct clients (cooperatives, farmers organizations...)	Suppliers & Clients	Galician association of agro cooperatives
Agricultural Industry Associations	Civil society organisation	Experts in extensive rancher
Agriculture newspapers	Media	Agriculture TV informative
Labor Unions and syndicate	Workers & Farmers	Professional association of agronomical engineers

Soil experts	Education, Research	Experts in soil science
Agricultural Industry Associations	Civil society organisation	Rancher association
Farmers and agricultural producers (livestock owners included)	Workers & Farmers	Ranchers. Native breeds. Extensive management
Health organisms	Civil society organisation	Farmer specialised in animals for mental health therapy purposes
Farmers and agricultural producers (livestock owners included)	Workers & Farmers	Ecological farm interested in sustainability and environmental education
Eco or nature tourism	Finance & Business	Ecological farm interested in environmental education
Farmers and agricultural producers (livestock owners included)	Workers & Farmers	Interested in the relation between different vine culture management systems
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Regional governing authority in rural development
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Responsible department at a provincial level
Site responsible Owners and managers of the agricultural site	Workers & Farmers	Not known
Site responsible Owners and managers of the agricultural site	Workers & Farmers	No known
Site responsible Owners and managers of the agricultural site	Workers & Farmers	Owner of the land
Site responsible Owners and managers of the agricultural site	Workers & Farmers	Agricultural exploitation in the land
Site responsible Owners and managers of the agricultural site	Workers & Farmers	Owner of the land
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Public body responsible for the management of the Miño-Sil river basin

Table 22: Stakeholder identification Atlantic agricultural land use site

Figure 22 details the overall distribution of stakeholder groups in this site.

Fig.22: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Atlantic agricultural land use site

Civil society organisations: Three civil society organizations have been identified, including two agricultural industry associations and one health organization. One agricultural association focuses on the study, management, and promotion of sustainable pasture and agricultural systems, while the other supports livestock farmers and advocates for sustainable farming practices. The health organization is dedicated to the use of animals for mental health support. Although these stakeholders are external to the site, they provide valuable expertise for land management and sustainability.

Education, Research: The education/research stakeholder category is the second largest, comprising six stakeholders. This includes institutions specializing in soil expertise, such as a technical soil company, and an organization with knowledge in ecological management and ranching. Other stakeholders in this category include research centres focused on specific agricultural studies.

Finance & Business: This category includes a single stakeholder: a farm that offers environmental education to tourists and visitors.

Media: Two regional agricultural media outlets are linked to the site, including an online newspaper and an agricultural TV channel, both providing informative news on farming practices.

Public bodies: Four regional and local public bodies have been identified, including the regional government authority for rural development, the local department responsible for territorial oversight, the public confederation managing the nearby river basin, and a public office providing advisory services on local agricultural matters.

Suppliers & Clients: The experimental site also includes four stakeholders in the suppliers and client's category. These stakeholders consist of suppliers of fertilizers and clients involved in purchasing cattle and food products.

Workers & Farmers: This category is the largest group of stakeholders, with a total of 12 workers and farmers identified. It includes ranchers and livestock breeders, a professional association of agronomical engineers, regional farmers interested in agricultural and land management practices, as well as local landowners and site managers who are primarily responsible for land management.

Agricultural land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 23 maps the stakeholder groups of the agricultural experimental site across their interest and influence in the project.

Fig.23: Stakeholder mapping Atlantic agricultural land use site

The stakeholder mapping reveals some interesting patterns regarding the level of interest and influence among various groups. Surprisingly, farmers and workers, as well as public body authorities, exhibit generally lower levels of interest in the project compared to other sites. Important to note is that within the farmer and worker category, site managers show a relatively higher influence compared to farmers directly working on the land. This is understandable, as site managers typically hold greater decision-making authority over the site. However, it is worth noting that site managers also displayed lower interest compared to farmers. Another key observation is the high level of interest demonstrated by many stakeholders in the project, despite their overall limited influence on the site. Nevertheless, their interest

in the project, combined with their sector-specific knowledge, holds significant potential to add valuable contributions.

Mining land use: stakeholder identification

Table 23 summarises the characteristics of the Atlantic mining land use site.

Atlantic mining land use site

Mining Land Use: Gravel production Mission Soil: Recultivation and renaturation	
Extension	1.4 ha
Description geographical context	The Puga gravel quarry, located in the Toén council, has been in operation since the 1990s. Current soil pressures or management practices have persisted for over 10 years. The soils within the quarry are predominantly technosols resulting from quarrying activities, with some leptosols present in the surrounding areas.
Soil Health Pressures	Biodiversity loss, organic matter loss, compaction, contamination
Soil Health Practices	Afforestation and/or natural rejuvenation
Intensity 1	Quarry. Non restored area. No vegetation or small trees plus bushes
Intensity 2	Partially restored area with pine afforestation and shrubs implantation
Intensity 3	Surrounding forest (no quarry activity). Pine afforestation

Table 23: Atlantic mining land use site

The Atlantic mining experimental site a total of 8 stakeholders identified.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Regional governing authority in economy, industry and innovation
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Regional government department for energy planning and natural resources
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Responsible department at a provincial level
Mining companies	Workers & Farmers	Mining company interested in ecological restoration
NGO on industrial heritage conservation	Civil society organisation	Association for the industrial heritage conservation
Site responsible / owners and entities owning the area	Workers & Farmers	Association owning the site
Companies working on this site	Workers & Farmers	Mining company worker
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Public body responsible for the management of the Miño-Sil river basin

Table 24: Stakeholder identification Atlantic mining land use site

Figure 24 details the overall distribution of these stakeholders.

Fig.24: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Atlantic mining land use site

Civil society organisation: One NGO connected to the site focuses on the conservation of industrial heritage.

Public bodies: This is the largest stakeholder category for the site, comprising four stakeholders: a regional governing authority focused on economic and industrial innovation, a department for energy, planning, and natural resources, the local public territory department, and the authority responsible for overseeing the nearby river basin.

Workers & Farmers: 3 stakeholders on this category are identified, including the association that owns the mining site, a mining company operating on it, and a mining company interested in the ecological restoration of mining sites.

Mining land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 25 maps the stakeholder groups of the Atlantic mining experimental site across their interest and influence in the project.

Fig.25: Stakeholder mapping Atlantic mining land use site

The mining site only has three stakeholder groups identified. The mapping reveals that workers and farmers, along with public body authorities, have significant influence over the mining site but show relatively low interest. Keeping them involved and minimally engaged is important as these stakeholders can have a lot of insights in the mining site’s environmental impact in the region. The NGO shows slight interest in the project but very limited influence. This stakeholder may view the project as an opportunity to contribute knowledge or gain insights, despite their lack of direct control over site activities.

Semi-natural land use: stakeholder identification

Table 25 summarises the characteristics of the Atlantic semi-natural land use site.

Atlantic semi-natural land use site

Semi-Natural Land Use: Abandoned pastures Mission Soil: Nature protection site	
Extension	0.5 to 0.6 ha
Description geographical context	These areas were cultivated until the 1970s, after which they were abandoned and transitioned to various forest types, including natural oak forests and pine plantations for wood production. Over the past 20 years, part of the area has been invaded by the alien species <i>Acacia dealbata</i> .
Soil Health Pressures	Biodiversity loss, potential soil compaction
Soil Health Practices	Afforestation and/or natural rejuvenation
Intensity 1	Alien species (<i>Acacia dealbata</i>)
Intensity 2	Artificial afforestation (pine)
Intensity 3	Natural recovery (Oaks and mixed Atlantic forest)

Table 25: Atlantic semi-natural land use site

The Atlantic semi-natural experimental site has 19 stakeholders connected to its site.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Regional governing authority in rural development
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Regional government department for forestry planning
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Responsible department at a provincial level
Fire management and disaster response authorities	Public bodies	Responsible department for mount and forest management at a local level
Farmers and agricultural producers (livestock owners included) or any type of producers working on this area	Workers & Farmers	Galician forestry association
Academics in agricultural, environmental science	Workers & Farmers	Professional association of forestry engineers
Academics in agricultural, environmental science	Workers & Farmers	Professional association of forestry engineers
Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Engineering company specialised in forestry, agricultural and environmental fields
Fire management and disaster response authorities	Civil society organisation	Firefighters association
Recreational and tourism industry (skiing, tourism infrastructures...)	Finance & Business	Ecotourism and environmental education company
Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Engineering company specialised in forestry, urban and environmental fields
Site responsible Owners and managers of the site	Workers & Farmers	Community of land owners in common hand that works in mount management from a multidisciplinary perspective
Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Engineering company specialised in forestry and urban fields
Eco or nature tourism (birdwatching, hunting, wildlife photography...)	Finance & Business	Ecotourism company
Soil experts	Education, Research	Expert in ecological restoration

Site responsible Owners and managers of the site	Workers & Farmers	End user
Site responsible Owners and managers of the site	Workers & Farmers	End user
Site responsible Owners and managers of the site	Workers & Farmers	End user
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Public body responsible for the management of the Miño-Sil river basin

Table 26: Stakeholder identification Atlantic semi-natural land use site

Figure 26 details the overall distribution of stakeholder groups in this site.

Fig.26: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Atlantic semi-natural land use site

Civil society organisation: One stakeholder belongs to this category part of an association of firefighters who work with an environmental approach.

Education, Research: This category is comprised out of one stakeholder, a soil expert organization specializing in soil ecological restoration.

Finance & Business: This category consists of two stakeholders from ecotourism companies.

Public bodies: Five regional and local public bodies have been identified, including the Department of Forestry Planning, the Department of Rural Development, the local governing body overseeing the territory, and the public confederation managing the nearby river basin.

Workers & Farmers: This category is the largest group once again, comprising ten stakeholders, including various site owners, professional associations of forestry engineers a regional forestry association working on

the land, and landscaping companies specializing in forestry management and landscaping.

Semi-natural land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 27 maps the stakeholder groups of the Atlantic semi-natural experimental site across their interest and influence in the project.

Fig.27: Stakeholder mapping Atlantic semi-natural land use site

The stakeholder mapping highlights a clear divide among stakeholder groups in terms of their levels of influence and interest. Within the workers and farmers category, there is a noticeable split: site managers tend to have higher influence but lower interest, while local landscaping companies and site workers show higher interest but lower influence. To account for both perspectives, this stakeholder group is positioned between the "Involve" and "Inform" boxes, allowing for a blended engagement strategy that ensures both groups are appropriately considered in the project.

Urban land use: stakeholder identification

Table 27 summarises the characteristics of the Atlantic urban land use site.

Atlantic urban land use site

Urban Land Use: Urban gardens and urban forest Mission Soil: Green space for leisure and aesthetic purposes	
Extension	0.5 ha
Description geographical context	The urban soils are located in the city of Ourense, a small city of about 100,000 inhabitants. The soils are located on the university campus (Intensities 1 and 2), while intensity 3 is within a pedestrian area near a small river. Intensity 1 was previously a hospital area, but since 1970s, was reconverted to a University campus area, Intensity 2 was previously an agricultural area and, since the 2000s, was reconverted to an Urban campus, while Intensity 3 has had the same use and vegetation since the 1950s.
Soil Health Pressures	Biodiversity loss, compaction, contamination, soil sealing
Soil Health Practices	Reduction of soil sealing by creating green spaces in urban areas. Green areas design and management
Intensity 1	Natural grasses with intense irrigation-clearing and closer to potential contamination sources (pedestrians, traffic road and residential areas)
Intensity 2	Natural grasses with less irrigation-clearing and further away from potential contamination sources
Intensity 3	Natural grasses without irrigation-herbicides. Near to a semi-natural areas.

Table 27: Atlantic urban land use site

The Atlantic urban experimental site also has 26 stakeholders identified to its site.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Regional governing authority in environment, territory and housing
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Regional government department for territory planning and urbanism
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Responsible department at a provincial level
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Institution linked to the regional government. Working fields: urbanism, territory planning, landscape.
Academics in urban design and policy makers	Education, Research	Professional association of architects
Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Spanish association of landscape architects
Urban planning firm	Workers & Farmers	Bioconstruction company
Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Landscape architecture company
Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Landscape architecture company
Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Landscape architecture company
Environmental and Conservation Organizations	Civil society organisation	Gardens and parks interpretation centre
Urban farmers	Workers & Farmers	Association working in urban orchard
Community gardeners	Workers & Farmers	Responsible for the maintenance of gardens and parks in Santiago de Compostela municipality
Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Landscape company interested in soil processes
Urban farmers	Workers & Farmers	Association working in urban orchards
Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Landscape architecture company
Urban farmers	Workers & Farmers	Flower farmer
Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Landscape architecture company

Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Landscape architecture company
Soil experts	Education, Research	Expert in archaeology
Urban planning firm	Workers & Farmers	Experts in urban planning, architecture and sustainable development
Urban planning firm	Workers & Farmers	Experts in sustainable development
Local media and bloggers	Media	Urban planning and regenerative agriculture company
Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Bioconstruction Galician association
Site responsible / owners and entities owning the area	Workers & Farmers	University
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Public body responsible for the management of the Miño-Sil river basin

Table 28: Stakeholder identification Atlantic urban land use site

Figure 28, displays the distribution of all the stakeholder categories for this site.

Fig.28: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Atlantic urban land use site

Civil society organisation: one foundation is connected to the site, which focuses on the conservation and creation of urban parks and gardens.

Education, Research: The two stakeholders in this category include an association of architects focused on urban design research and an expert in archaeology

Media: The identified media stakeholder is an organization dedicated to promoting sustainable architecture and ecological housing through various media channels.

Public bodies: Five public authorities have been identified, with departments overseeing different areas. Some are responsible for managing parts of the territory, while others oversee urbanism, planning, and housing.

Workers & Farmers: This is the largest category, consisting of 17 stakeholders. The size of this group reflects the diversity of workers involved in urban landscapes, including landscaping firms, architecture and construction companies, urban farmers and gardeners responsible for creating and maintaining urban parks and gardens, as well as other professionals engaged in urban planning and landscaping.

Urban land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 29 maps the stakeholder groups of the Atlantic urban land use site across their interest and influence in the project.

Fig.29: Stakeholder mapping Atlantic urban land use site

Stakeholders of the urban land use site generally exhibit a low level of influence over the site. This can be attributed to the challenges of making a significant impact on land situated within a university campus. In contrast, public body stakeholders have a higher degree of influence due to their decision-making authority. Landscaping companies and urban planning firms, part of the workers and farmers category, while capable of contributing to landscape design and architecture, are not directly involved in the site's operations, limiting their ability to make a meaningful impact.

Wetland land use: stakeholder identification

Table 29 summarises the characteristics of the Atlantic wetland land use site.

Atlantic wetland land use site

Wetland Land Use: Flooded areas under wet Season Mission Soil: Sustainable management	
Extension	1 ha
Description geographical context	All areas are located near a small river and experience flooding during winter and spring, sometimes extending into early summer. Management varies: Intensity 1 is a private garden with fruit trees and pet animals, where vegetation is cleared mechanically and chemically. Intensity 2 is an abandoned agricultural area, with vegetation cleared annually. Intensity 3, once agricultural until the 1970s, has since become a semi-natural riparian forest frequently subject to flooding.
Soil Health Pressures	Biodiversity loss, soil contamination (herbicides) and vegetation clearing
Soil Health Practices	No specific soil health practices
Intensity 1	Crops in summer and partially managed with vegetation clearing
Intensity 2	Frequently cleared areas
Intensity 3	Semi-natural area. Riparian forest

Table 29: Atlantic wetland land use site

The urban experimental site has 20 stakeholders identified.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Regional government authority in environment, territory and housing
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Regional government department for natural heritage
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Regional government department for environmental quality, sustainability and climate change
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Responsible department at a provincial level
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Institution linked to the regional government. Working fields: urbanism, territory planning, landscape.
Academics in agricultural, silviculture, environmental science	Education, Research	Institute of experts in nature conservation and Natura 2000 network management
Environmental and Conservation Organizations	Civil society organisation	Naturalist group specialised in habitat and species protection
Environmental and Conservation Organizations	Civil society organisation	Experts in wildlife, specialised in birds
NGO on conservation	Civil society organisation	Territory custody associations
NGO on conservation	Civil society organisation	Territory custody associations
Eco or nature tourism	Finance & Business	Company specialised in cultural, environmental and leisure services
NGO on conservation	Civil society organisation	Territory custody associations
Research organisms	Education, Research	Researchers and experts in environmental technology investigation, from de Santiago de Compostela University
Environmental and Conservation Organizations	Civil society organisation	Association for the ecological defence of Galicia
NGO on conservation	Civil society organisation	Association working for the conservation of sea and coastal environment
Site responsible Owners and managers of the wetland site	Workers & Farmers	End user

Site responsible Owners and managers of the wetland site	Workers & Farmers	End user
Site responsible Owners and managers of the wetland site	Workers & Farmers	End user
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Public body responsible for the management of the Miño-Sil river basin
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Regional government authority in cultural heritage

Table 30: Stakeholder identification Atlantic wetland land use site

Figure 30 details the overall distribution of stakeholder groups in this site.

Fig.30: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Atlantic wetland land use site

Public bodies: Seven stakeholders are identified in the public body category, including regional authorities from the Environment, Territory, and Housing; Natural Heritage; Environmental Quality and Climate Change; and Urbanism and Territorial Planning departments.

Education, Research: Two stakeholders belong to the education and research group, including an institute specializing in nature conservation and an expert in environmental technology investigation

Civil society organisation: This experimental site has a greater number of civil society stakeholders compared to others, with a total of seven identified in this category. These stakeholders belong to NGOs focused on territorial and environmental conservation, as well as species protection.

Finance & Business: One tourism business has been identified as a key stakeholder for this site. This company specializes in cultural, environmental, and leisure services.

Workers & Farmers: Three site responsible and owners have been identified here, consisting of the private landowners.

Wetland land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 31 maps the stakeholder groups of the Atlantic wetland land use site across their interest and influence in the project.

Fig.31: Stakeholder mapping Atlantic wetland land use site

The stakeholder mapping of the Atlantic wetland site reveals a generally high level of interest among stakeholders. NGOs and research institutions, in particular, demonstrate a strong willingness to actively engage in the project. While their direct influence on the specific site is limited, they still exert significant influence on its environmental performance, aligning with their focus on nature conservation, species protection and research. Site managers, on the other hand, have high influence over both the economic and environmental aspects of the site, highlighting the importance of their active involvement in the project to ensure balanced and effective outcomes.

8.1.3 Stakeholder identification and mapping Boreal sites

Agricultural land use: stakeholder identification

Table 31 summarises the characteristics of the Boreal agricultural land use site.

Boreal agricultural land use site

Agricultural Land Use Mission Soil: Reduction of deep drainage and mowing frequency	
Extension	13 ha
Description geographical context	Located in the central part of Latvia, this region is predominantly covered by forests. Agricultural land, primarily on peat soils, is managed for hay production and has been used for farming for at least two decades. The area lies in a lowland region characterized by peat and waterlogged soils. The impact of the melioration system varies in intensity across different parts of the landscape.
Soil Health Pressures	Melioration, nutrient imbalance
Soil Health Practices	Mowing intensity, regulation of water table level
Intensity 1	Annual cropping system , high intensity drainage, mowing three times per season
Intensity 2	Annual/Perennial cropping system, medium intensity drainage, mowing no more than two times per season
Intensity 3	Woody/Perennial cropping system, low intensity drainage, mowing no more than two times per season

Table 31: Boreal agricultural land use site

The Boreal agricultural site has a total of 29 stakeholders connected to the site.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Site responsible Owners and managers of the agricultural site	Workers & Farmers	Deputy forester of Tireļi forestry
Farmers and agricultural producers (livestock owners included)	Workers & Farmers	Member of Farmers parliament
Workers, former workers	Workers & Farmers	Forest manager who rent agriculture land from Riga city
Agricultural Industry Associations	Civil society organisation	Board member. cooperation among agricultural organizations in Latvia
professional association that focuses on the development and advocacy of agronomy as a field	Civil society organisation	NGO president, education of agronomists. professional association that focuses on the development and advocacy of agronomy as a field
Suppliers and subcontractors (i.e agricultural inputs, seeds, fertilizers, equipment...)	Suppliers & Clients	Chairman of the board
state-owned financial institution	Public bodies	Chairman of the board / Public Relations Manager. state-owned financial institution in Latvia that provides financing solutions to support
Direct clients (cooperatives, farmers organizations...)	Suppliers & Clients	Chairman of the board
Indirect clients (retailers, consumers...)	Suppliers & Clients	Agriculture/ Animal husbandry division lead specialists
Rural Communities and Residents organizations	Public bodies	Spatial planning. governmental institution established to coordinate regional development and planning at a larger scale
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Department of Agriculture and Rural Development Deputy Director of the Department
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Department of Spatial Planning and Land Management, Director

Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Climate Policy Department, Director
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Department of Agriculture and Rural Development, Director
Environmental and Conservation Organizations (environmental impacts of agri practices and could advocate for sust.and ecofriendly farming..)	Public bodies	Department of nature conservation, Director.
NGO on agricultural or rural development	Civil society organisation	Local coordinator of NovaSoil
NGO on agricultural or rural development	Civil society organisation	Advisor on environmental protection issues.
Health organisms	Public bodies	Soil Agrochemical Research Division , director Public body: part of Ministry of Agriculture of Latvia
Research organisms	Education, Research	Head of Department/ Environmental Expert/ Leading Researcher, Bioeconomy Department
Research organisms	Education, Research	Not known
Research organisms	Education, Research	Agrochemistry research
Academics in agricultural, environmental science and economics	Education, Research	Institute of Soil and Plant Sciences Director of the Institute
Academics in agricultural, environmental science and economics	Education, Research	Department of Geography, Acting Head: Associate Professor
Soil experts	Education, Research	Institute of Soil and Plant Sciences - Professor (Emeritus); Leading Researcher
Soil experts	Education, Research	Institute of Soil and Plant Sciences - Associate Professor (tenure)
Finance partners	Finance & Business	CEO of Riga city forest
Eco or nature tourism	Finance & Business	Tourism and Environment Expert
Local media and bloggers	Media	Editor-in-Chief
Agriculture newspapers	Media	Not Known

Table 32: Stakeholder identification Boreal agricultural land use site

The distribution of stakeholder categories for this site is displayed in Figure 32.

Fig.32: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Boreal agricultural land use site

Civil society organisation: Four stakeholders belong to the civil society organization category. This group includes NGOs advocating for the interests of agricultural organizations and farmers, as well as a professional organization dedicated to advancing the development and knowledge within the agricultural sector.

Education & Research: This is the second largest stakeholder group for the site, comprising seven stakeholders. The group primarily consists of experts from research institutions and university faculties specializing in soil health, plant science, and agrochemistry.

Finance & Business: This group includes two stakeholders, one being a Latvian tourism association that promotes rural tourism and the other a financial partner supporting the city.

Media: Two media stakeholders have been identified, including one individual working at a professional magazine focused on agricultural and rural issues, and another at a daily newspaper.

Public bodies: This is the largest stakeholder group for the site, comprising eight stakeholders. These stakeholders are affiliated with state-owned financial institutions and governmental bodies linked to regional development and planning. They work in departments focused on agriculture and rural development, spatial planning, public policy, and environmental protection.

Suppliers & Clients: Three stakeholders belong to this group, one supplier offering services to help farmers manage and enhance their agricultural activities, and two organizations providing consulting, education, and training services.

Workers & Farmers: Three stakeholders belong to this group, including the site manager, an organization conducting agricultural activities and beekeeping on the site, and a forest manager who rents the land from the city of Riga. It is important to note that, while these site owners and managers are part of the Workers & Farmers category as they directly oversee the site, their organisations are considered public bodies, as the site is publicly owned by the state of Latvia.

Agricultural land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 33 maps the stakeholder groups of the Boreal agricultural land use site across their interest and influence in the project.

Fig.33: Stakeholder mapping Boreal agricultural land use site

The stakeholder map for the Boreal agricultural site indicates that the overall influence of most stakeholder types tends to be at a medium level, resulting in many stakeholder groups falling into different engagement categories. Therefore, it is crucial to invite stakeholders to co-creation activities that align with their areas of expertise, ensuring they have opportunities to engage with our work packages and partners.

Public body stakeholders hold the highest influence over the site, which is expected given their roles in policymaking and their direct impact on site activities, such as agricultural development and environmental protection. The site remains state-owned, which explains the strong connection and influence public authorities have over it. However, management of the site is carried out by the site owners, who lease the land from the City of Riga.

This arrangement helps explain why the site managers' interests in the project may be higher compared to those of public bodies.

Forest land use: stakeholder identification

Table 33 summarises the characteristics of the Boreal forest land use site.

Boreal forest land use site

Forest Land Use Mission Soil: Reduction of anthropogenic eutrophication	
Extension	28 ha
Description geographical context	Pinus sylvestris-dominated boreal forests growing on histosol in a lowland region characterized by peat and waterlogged soils. The dominant tree species have an average age of 80 years. The first intensity site is situated near the city, experiencing higher levels of anthropogenic impact.
Soil Health Pressures	Nutrient imbalance, Acidification & Eutrophication
Soil Health Practices	Management by ensuring an appropriate understory density, limiting anthropogenic pressure
Intensity 1	Forest on mineral soil with nutrient imbalance (Acidification), anthropogenic eutrophication
Intensity 2	Forest on mineral soil with Eutrophication, dense forest understory, no anthropogenic pollution
Intensity 3	Oligotroph, normal to low density forest, boreal forest with typical forest vegetation, understory is sparse

Table 33: Boreal forest land use site

The Boreal forest site has a total of 40 stakeholders connected to the site, 8 of which belong to the Latvian State Forest Research Institute (SILAVA), who is the coordinating organization for the Boreal experimental sites.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Local media and bloggers	Media	Main redactor
The Forest Research Station	Education, Research	Senior Support Expert
The Forest Research Station	Education, Research	Director
Forestry and Logging companies	Education, Research	Deputy director
Forestry and Logging companies	Workers & Farmers	Forestry Planning Manager
Forestry and Logging companies	Workers & Farmers	Responsible for forest regeneration
Site responsible Owners and managers of forest site	Workers & Farmers	Deputy forester of Tireļi forestry
Site responsible Owners and managers of forest site	Workers & Farmers	CEO of Riga city forest
Landscaping companies	Public bodies	Head of division
Timber Industry Associations	Civil society organisation	Executive Director
Labor Unions and syndicate	Civil society organisation	Chairperson
Energy & Biomass Industry (companies of)	Civil society organisation	Chairman of the Board
Energy & Biomass Industry (companies of)	Civil society organisation	Certification Coordinator
Rural Communities and Residents organizations	Residents, citizens	General contact
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Department of Spatial Planning and Land Management, Director
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Climate Policy Department, Director
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Department of Forests, Director
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Department of Agriculture and Rural Development, Director
Environmental and Conservation Organizations	Public bodies	Department of nature conservation, Director

NGO on agricultural or rural development	Civil society organisation	Chairman of the Board
NGO on agricultural or rural development	Civil society organisation	Chairman of the Board
Research organisms	Education, Research	Not known
Research organisms	Education, Research	Director of institute
Soil experts	Education, Research	Sc. assistant. soil and water handling soaking
Soil experts	Education, Research	Sc. assistant. soil and biodiversity
Soil experts	Education, Research	Sc. assistant. soil and watertable
Soil experts	Education, Research	Head of environmental lab, senior researcher
Soil experts	Education, Research	Senior researcher / GHG flues environmentalist
Soil experts	Education, Research	Researcher Soil analysis and modelling
Soil experts	Education, Research	Researcher Soil an carbon
Soil experts	Education, Research	Researcher Soil, trees and economics
Soil experts	Education, Research	Institute of Soil and Plant Sciences - Associate Professor (tenure)
Local media and bloggers	Media	Journalist
Local media and bloggers	Media	Broadcast moderator
Local media and bloggers	Media	News and thematic broadcasts
Academics in environment, geology	Education, Research	Researcher and teacher on biodiversity and other sciences
Academics in environment, geology	Education, Research	Researcher and teacher on earth and other sciences
Academics in environment, geology	Education, Research	Faculty of forestry and environmental sciences
Environmental newspaper	Media	Publish data, informs forestry and related sector
Environmental and Conservation Organizations	Public bodies	Department of nature conservation, director

Table 34: Stakeholder identification Boreal forest land use site

The distribution of stakeholder categories for this site is displayed in Figure 34.

Fig.34: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Boreal forest land use site

Civil society organisation: This group includes six stakeholders, comprising organizations that represent businesses, workers, hunters, and forest owners within the forestry industry, as well as organizations representing stakeholders in the biomass sector.

Education & Research: This is the largest group, comprising 17 stakeholders from research and academic institutions engaged in studies related to forestry practices, forest ecosystems, environmental protection, soil science, and more. The group also includes 8 soil experts from the Latvian State Forest Research Institute (Silava), which serves as the coordinating organization for the Boreal experimental sites.

Media: Five stakeholders belong to the media category, working for local newspapers, broadcasters, and journals focused on forestry.

Public bodies: Seven public body representatives have been identified, working in nature protection and conservation, planning departments, and within the Ministry of Agriculture, as well as in the ministry of climate and energy.

Residents, citizens: This stakeholder represents a community-based organization in Riga focused on improving quality of life for residents.

Workers & Farmers: Four stakeholders belong to this category, including a forestry planning manager and the site owners. Again, it is important to note that, while these site owners and managers are part of the Workers &

Farmers category as they directly oversee the site, they are also considered public bodies, as the site is publicly owned by the state of Latvia.

Forest land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 35 maps the stakeholder groups of the Boreal forest land use site across their interest and influence in the project.

Fig.35: Stakeholder mapping Boreal forest land use site

The stakeholder map of the forest site highlights that stakeholders connected to the site possess a medium to high level of influence over its management and activities. This is particularly valuable for the project, as it enables direct collaboration with various stakeholder groups that can actively shape site activities and significantly impact soil health management practices.

Additionally, the map identifies the resident community as a highly influential group with a strong interest in sustainable forestry management practices. Given their vested interest, it is crucial to engage this local stakeholder group in co-creation activities, as their involvement can contribute valuable local knowledge, foster long-term commitment to sustainable practices and help raise awareness for soil health.

Furthermore, research institutions emerge as the most highly engaged stakeholder group, with the highest level of interest in the site. Notably, this group includes eight stakeholders from SILAVA, the coordinating body for the Boreal experimental sites. Their expertise and scientific contributions play a pivotal role in advancing sustainable forest management strategies and ensuring the integration of research-driven best practices.

Mining land use: stakeholder identification

Table 35 summarises the characteristics of the Boreal mining land use site.

Boreal mining land use site

Mining Land Use Mission Soil: Reduction of post-mining mineralization and GHG emissions	
Extension	32 ha
Description geographical context	Abandoned peat extraction site affected by long-term melioration since at least the 1960s, with peat extraction ceasing in 1994. Situated in a lowland region dominated by peat soils, the area experiences slow natural restoration, particularly in zones with a well-functioning melioration ditch system. Restoration is hindered by several plant growth-limiting factors, including low soil moisture, high soil acidity, nutrient imbalance, intense solar radiation, and soil erosion.
Soil Health Pressures	Biodiversity loss, Erosion & OM mineralization
Soil Health Practices	Reclamation and restoration
Intensity 1	The first restoration stage: Sand extraction ended 5-10 years ago. Post-mining site without management
Intensity 2	The second restoration stage: Sand extraction ended 10-20 years ago. Post-mining site with afforestation practice
Intensity 3	The third restoration stage: Sand extraction ended 20-30 years ago. Post mining site with restoration practice increasing water table level

Table 35: Boreal mining land use site

The Boreal mining site has a total of 46 stakeholders identified, 8 of which belong to the Latvian State Forest Research Institute (SILAVA), who is the coordinating organization for the Boreal experimental sites.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Site responsible Owners and managers of the mining site	Workers & Farmers	Ranger
Mining companies Associations	Workers & Farmers	Member of board
Site responsible Owners and managers of the mining site	Workers & Farmers	Member of board
Finance partners	Finance & Business	Former peat mining site restoring manager/ Environmental engineer
Finance partners	Finance & Business	Director construction materials and peat
Mining companies	Finance & Business	Finance and Administrative Director
Mining companies	Finance & Business	Executive Director
Mining companies	Finance & Business	Board member
Local media and bloggers	Media	Main redactor
The Forest Research Station	Education, Research	Senior Support Expert
The Forest Research Station	Education, Research	Director
Forestry and Logging companies	Education, Research	Deputy director
Forestry and Logging companies	Workers & Farmers	Forestry Planning Manager
Forestry and Logging companies	Workers & Farmers	Responsible for forest regeneration
Site responsible Owners and managers of forest site	Workers & Farmers	Deputy forester of Tireļi forestry
Site responsible Owners and managers of forest site	Workers & Farmers	CEO of Riga city forest
Landscaping companies	Public bodies	head of division
Energy & Biomass Industry (companies of)	Civil society organisation	Chairman of the Board
Energy & Biomass Industry (companies of)	Civil society organisation	Certification Coordinator
Rural Communities and Residents organizations	Residents, citizens	General contact
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Department of Spatial Planning and Land Management, Director

Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Climate Policy Department, Director
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Department of Forests, Director
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Department of Agriculture and Rural Development, Director
Environmental and Conservation Organizations	Public bodies	Department of nature conservation, Director
NGO on agricultural or rural development	Civil society organisation	Chairman of the Board
NGO on agricultural or rural development	Civil society organisation	Member of board
Research organisms	Education, Research	Not Known
Research organisms	Education, Research	Director of institute
Soil experts	Education, Research	Sc. assistant. soil and water handling soaking
Soil experts	Education, Research	Sc. assistant. soil and biodiversity
Soil experts	Education, Research	Sc. assistant. soil and watertable
Soil experts	Education, Research	Head of environmental lab, senior researcher
Soil experts	Education, Research	Senior researcher / GHG flues environmentalist
Soil experts	Education, Research	researcher Soil analysis and modelling
Soil experts	Education, Research	Researcher Soil an carbon
Soil experts	Education, Research	Researcher Soil, trees and economics
Soil experts	Education, Research	Institute of Soil and Plant Sciences - Associate Professor (tenure)
Local media and bloggers	Media	Journalist
Local media and bloggers	Media	broadcast moderator
Local media and bloggers	Media	News and thematic broadcasts
Academics in environment, geology	Education, Research	Researcher and teacher on biodiversity and other sciences
Academics in environment, geology	Education, Research	Researcher and teacher on earth and other sciences
Academics in environment, geology	Education, Research	Faculty of forestry and environmental sciences
Environmental newspaper	Media	publish data, informs forestry and related sector

Environmental and Conservation Organizations	Civil society organisation	Department of nature conservation, Director
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Table 36: Stakeholder identification Boreal mining land use site

The distribution of stakeholder categories for this site is displayed in Figure 36. Many stakeholders of the mining site are also included in the forest site, as the mining site is situated within an afforested area.

Fig.36: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Boreal mining land use site

Civil society organisation: This group includes five stakeholders, comprising organizations that represent businesses and workers within the forestry, peat and nature conservation industry, as well as organizations representing stakeholders in the biomass sector.

Education & Research: This is the largest group, comprising 17 stakeholders from research and academic institutions focused on forest science and management, as well as organizations addressing environmental challenges and soil health practices. The group also includes 8 soil experts from the Latvian State Forest Research Institute (Silava), which coordinates the Boreal experimental sites.

Finance & Business: Five stakeholders belong to this category including finance partners to the site and companies who are linked to the mining activities conducted at the site.

Media: Five stakeholders belong to the media category, working for local newspapers, broadcasters, and journals focused on forestry.

Public bodies: Six public body representatives have been identified, working in nature protection and conservation, planning departments, and

within the Ministry of Agriculture, as well as in the ministry of climate and energy.

Residents, citizens: This stakeholder represents a community-based organization in Riga focused on improving quality of life for residents.

Workers & Farmers: Seven stakeholders belong to this category, including the site owners, managers, and planners. It is important to note that, while these site owners and managers fall under the Workers & Farmers category due to their direct oversight of the site, they are also considered public bodies, as the site is publicly owned by the state of Latvia.

Mining land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 37 maps the stakeholder groups of the Boreal mining land use site across their interest and influence in the project.

Fig.37: Stakeholder mapping Boreal mining land use site

The stakeholder map of the mining land-use site closely resembles that of the forest land-use site, with stakeholder groups exhibiting similar levels of influence and interest. However, a notable exception is the civil society organizations category, which demonstrates both greater influence over the mining site and a higher level of interest in the project.

This increased involvement may be attributed to the significant environmental impact of mining activities and the critical role these organizations play in advocating for stronger nature conservation policies. Their heightened influence suggests an opportunity to collaborate more

effectively on sustainable land management strategies and environmental protection initiatives within the mining context.

Semi-natural land use: stakeholder identification

Table 37 summarises the characteristics of the Boreal semi-natural land use site.

Boreal semi-natural land use site

Semi-Natural Land Use Mission Soil: Decreased organic matter loss in intensive tree plantation	
Extension	62 ha
Description geographical context	Selective stripe-planted forests dominated by 30-year-old spruce, located in a lowland region characterized by peat soils. Afforestation with the same species (spruce) in felled interlines increases biological homogeneity, making the forest more vulnerable to pests, particularly the spruce eight-toothed bark beetle. However, the presence of deciduous species in interlines helps mitigate these risks by enhancing biodiversity and ecosystem resilience.
Soil Health Pressures	Organic material loss & Compaction
Soil Health Practices	Drainage regulation, selection of cultivated species
Intensity 1	Selective stripe cutting forest with spruce, high drainage
Intensity 2	Selective stripe cutting forest with spruce and birch, high drainage
Intensity 3	Selective stripe cutting forest with spruce and birch, low drainage

Table 37: Boreal semi-natural land use site

The Boreal semi-natural site has a total of 39 identified stakeholders, including eight from the Latvian State Forest Research Institute (SILAVA), the coordinating organization for the Boreal experimental sites.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Local media and bloggers	Media	Main redactor
The Forest Research Station	Education, Research	Senior Support Expert
The Forest Research Station	Education, Research	Director
Forestry and Logging companies	Education, Research	Deputy director
Forestry and Logging companies	Workers & Farmers	Forestry Planning Manager
Forestry and Logging companies	Workers & Farmers	Responsible for forest regeneration
Site responsible Owners and managers of forest site	Workers & Farmers	Deputy forester of Tireļi forestry
Site responsible Owners and managers of forest site	Workers & Farmers	CEO of Riga city forest
Landscaping companies	Public bodies	Head of division
Timber Industry Associations	Civil society organisation	Executive Director
Labor Unions and syndicate	Civil society organisation	Chairperson
Energy & Biomass Industry	Civil society organisation	Chairman of the Board
Energy & Biomass Industry	Civil society organisation	Certification Coordinator
Rural Communities and Residents organizations	Residents, citizens	General contact
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Department of Spatial Planning and Land Management, Director
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Climate Policy Department, Director
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Department of Agriculture and Rural Development, Director
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Department of Forests, Director
Environmental and Conservation Organizations	Public bodies	Department of nature conservation, Director
NGO on agricultural or rural development	Civil society organisation	Chairman of the Board

NGO on agricultural or rural development	Civil society organisation	Chairman of the Board
Research organisms	Education, Research	Not known
Research organisms	Education, Research	Director of institute
Soil experts	Education, Research	Sc. assistant. soil and water handling soaking
Soil experts	Education, Research	Sc. assistant. soil and biodiversity
Soil experts	Education, Research	Sc. assistant. soil and watertable
Soil experts	Education, Research	Head of environmental lab, senior researcher
Soil experts	Education, Research	Senior researcher / GHG flues environmentalist
Soil experts	Education, Research	researcher Soil analysis and modelling
Soil experts	Education, Research	Researcher Soil an carbon
Soil experts	Education, Research	Researcher Soil, trees and economics
Soil experts	Education, Research	Economist
Local media and bloggers	Media	Institute of Soil and Plant Sciences - Associate Professor (tenure)
Local media and bloggers	Media	Journalist
Local media and bloggers	Media	Broadcast moderator
Academics in environment, geology	Education, Research	News and thematic broadcasts
Academics in environment, geology	Education, Research	Researcher and teacher on earth and other sciences
Academics in environment, geology	Education, Research	Faculty of forestry and environmental sciences
Environmental newspaper	Media	Faculty of forestry and environmental sciences

Table 38: Stakeholder identification Boreal semi-natural land use site

The stakeholder list for this site is very similar to that of the Boreal forest experimental site, as both sites focus on forested areas. The distribution of stakeholder categories for this site is displayed in Figure 38.

Fig.38: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Boreal semi-natural land use site

Civil society organisation: This group includes six stakeholders, comprising organizations that represent businesses, workers, hunters, and forest owners within the forestry industry, as well as organizations representing stakeholders in the biomass sector.

Education & Research: This is the largest group, comprising 17 stakeholders from research and academic institutions engaged in studies related to forestry practices, forest ecosystems, environmental protection, soil science, and more. The group also includes 8 soil experts from the Latvian State Forest Research Institute (SILAVA), which serves as the coordinating organization for the Boreal experimental sites.

Media: Five stakeholders belong to the media category, working for local newspapers, broadcasters, and journals focused on forestry.

Public bodies: Six public body representatives have been identified, working in nature protection and conservation, planning departments, and within the Ministry of Agriculture, as well as in the ministry of climate and energy.

Residents, citizens: This stakeholder represents a community-based organization in Riga focused on improving quality of life for residents.

Workers & Farmers: Four stakeholders belong to this category, including a forestry planning manager and the site owners. Again, it is important to note that, while these site owners and managers are part of the Workers & Farmers category as they directly oversee the site, they are also considered public bodies, as the site is publicly owned by the state of Latvia.

Semi-natural land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 39 maps the stakeholder groups of the Boreal semi-natural land use site across their interest and influence in the project.

Fig.39: Stakeholder mapping Boreal semi-natural land use site

The stakeholder map is similar to the stakeholder map from the forest experimental site and provides similar insights.

Wetland land use: stakeholder identification

Table 39 summarises the characteristics of the Boreal wetland land use site.

Boreal wetland land use site

Wetland Land Use Mission Soil: Decreased organic matter loss, better habitat for wetland species	
Extension	35 ha
Description geographical context	Black alder wetland forests in central Latvia are influenced by a historical melioration network, particularly along the forest periphery. These areas, situated in lowland regions dominated by peat and waterlogged soils, experience increased soil degradation due to well-functioning drainage ditches, which contribute to ongoing water loss and organic matter depletion. However, blocking these ditches helps raise the water table, supporting wetland habitat restoration and overall ecosystem health.
Soil Health Pressures	Drainage, Organic matter loss, Habitat loss for wetland species
Soil Health Practices	Enhancing biodiversity, preserving rare natural areas
Intensity 1	High intensity drainage, high, standing groundwater level, methylated mercury is formed, low productivity
Intensity 2	Medium intensity drainage, groundwater is high, but water movement is limited, the forest productivity is low
Intensity 3	Low intensity drainage, groundwater level is high, but water is moving and rich with oxygen and nutrients (productive)

Table 39: Boreal wetland land use site

The Boreal wetland site has a total of 40 stakeholders identified, 8 of which belong to the Latvian State Forest Research Institute (Silava), who is the coordinating organization for the Boreal experimental sites. The stakeholder list for this site is again very similar to that of the Boreal forest and semi-natural experimental sites, as both sites focus on forested areas.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Local media and bloggers	Media	main redactor
The Forest Research Station	Education, Research	Senior Support Expert
The Forest Research Station	Education, Research	Director
Forestry and Logging companies	Education, Research	Deputy director
Forestry and Logging companies	Workers & Farmers	Forestry Planning Manager
Forestry and Logging companies	Workers & Farmers	responsible for forest regeneration
Site responsible Owners and managers of forest site	Workers & Farmers	Deputy forester of Tireļi forestry
Site responsible Owners and managers of forest site	Workers & Farmers	CEO of Riga city forest
Landscaping companies	Public bodies	Head of division
Timber Industry Associations	Civil society organisation	Executive Director
Labor Unions and syndicate	Civil society organisation	Chairperson
Energy & Biomass Industry	Civil society organisation	Chairman of the Board
Energy & Biomass Industry	Civil society organisation	Certification Coordinator
Rural Communities and Residents organizations	Residents, citizens	General contact
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Department of Spatial Planning and Land Management, Director
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Climate Policy Department, Director
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Department of Forests, Director
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Department of Agriculture and Rural Development, Director

Environmental and Conservation Organizations	Public bodies	Department of nature conservation, Director
NGO on agricultural or rural development	Civil society organisation	Chairman of the Board
NGO on agricultural or rural development	Civil society organisation	Chairman of the Board
Research organisms	Education, Research	Not known
Research organisms	Education, Research	Director of institute
Soil experts	Education, Research	Sc. assistant. soil and water handling soaking
Soil experts	Education, Research	Sc. assistant. soil and biodiversity
Soil experts	Education, Research	Sc. assistant. soil and watertable
Soil experts	Education, Research	Head of environmental lab, senior researcher
Soil experts	Education, Research	Senior researcher / GHG flues environmentalist
Soil experts	Education, Research	Researcher Soil analysis and modelling
Soil experts	Education, Research	Researcher Soil an carbon
Soil experts	Education, Research	Researcher Soil, trees and economics
Soil experts	Education, Research	Esosystem services
Local media and bloggers	Media	Institute of Soil and Plant Sciences - Associate Professor (tenure)
Local media and bloggers	Media	journalist
Local media and bloggers	Media	Broadcast moderator
Academics in environment, geology	Education, Research	News and thematic broadcasts
Academics in environment, geology	Education, Research	Researcher and teacher on biodiversity and other sciences
Academics in environment, geology	Education, Research	Researcher and teacher on earth and other sciences
Environmental newspaper	Media	Faculty of forestry and environmental sciences
Environmental and Conservation Organizations	Civil society organisation	publish data, informs forestry and related sector

Table 40: Stakeholder identification Boreal wetland land use site

The distribution of stakeholder categories for this site is displayed in Figure 40.

Fig.40: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Boreal wetland land use site

Civil society organisation: This group includes seven stakeholders, comprising organizations that represent businesses, workers, hunters, and forest owners within the forestry industry, as well as organizations representing stakeholders in the biomass sector.

Education & Research: This is the largest group, comprising 17 stakeholders from research and academic institutions engaged in studies related to forestry practices, forest ecosystems, environmental protection, soil science, and more. The group also includes 8 soil experts from the Latvian State Forest Research Institute (Silava), which serves as the coordinating organization for the Boreal experimental sites.

Media: Five stakeholders belong to the media category, working for local newspapers, broadcasters, and journals focused on forestry.

Public bodies: Six public body representatives have been identified, working in nature protection and conservation, planning departments, and within the Ministry of Agriculture, as well as in the ministry of climate and energy.

Residents, citizens: This stakeholder represents a community-based organization in Riga focused on improving quality of life for residents.

Workers & Farmers: Four stakeholders belong to this category, including a forestry planning manager and the site owners. Again, it is important to note that, while these site owners and managers are part of the Workers & Farmers category as they directly oversee the site, they are also considered public bodies, as the site is publicly owned by the state of Latvia.

Wetland land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 41 maps the stakeholder groups of the Boreal wetland land use site across their interest and influence in the project.

Fig.41: Stakeholder mapping Boreal wetland land use site

The stakeholder map is again similar to the stakeholder map from the forest and semi-natural experimental sites and provides similar insights.

8.1.4 Stakeholder identification and mapping Continental sites

Agricultural land use: stakeholder identification

Table 41 summarises the characteristics of the Continental agricultural land use site.

Continental agricultural land use site

Agricultural Land Use: Crop rotation in commercial farms Mission Soil: Reduction of management intensity	
Extension	1.5 to 8 ha
Description geographical context	The sites are located in an agricultural landscape with small villages, with Nideggen as the nearest small city. This hilly region is characterized by predominantly loamy soils. The long-term average temperature is 8.8°C, with an average annual precipitation of 600 mm
Soil Health Pressures	Biodiversity loss, compaction, erosion
Soil Health Practices	Reduction of high-input crops (here: maize) in a crop rotation to reduce management intensity and to reach out for more sustainability
Intensity 1	2 times cultivation of maize within 5 years
Intensity 2	1 time cultivation of maize within 5 years
Intensity 3	No cultivation of maize within 5 years

Table 41: Continental agricultural land use site

A total of 6 stakeholders are identified for the continental experimental site with agricultural land use.

Stakeholders Continental agricultural land use site

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Site responsible Owners and managers of the agricultural site	Workers & Farmers	Management of urban green space and playgrounds
NGO on agricultural or rural development	Civil society organisation	Interested in the study
Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Coordinator of experimental sites and public exchange
Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Organising the experimental sites and public exchange
Academics in agricultural, environmental science and economics	Education, Research	Scientific coordination of sampling and analysis
Academics in agricultural, environmental science and economics	Education, Research	Regional coordinator

Table 42: Stakeholder identification Continental agricultural land use site

Figure 42 shows the distribution of stakeholder groups in this site.

Fig.42: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Continental agricultural land use site

Civil society organisations: One nature conservation foundation is identified, demonstrating an interest in the research conducted at the site.

While limited in number, the presence of a nature conservation foundation signifies a commitment to environmental impact of the site.

Education, Research: This category includes two stakeholders from the Thünen-Institute, the coordinating organization for these continental experimental sites.

Workers & Farmers: This group comprises three stakeholders, including the site manager and two representatives from a company responsible for coordinating and organizing the experimental sites. This group underscores the importance of on-the-ground expertise and operational activities in the site.

Agricultural land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 43 maps the stakeholder categories across their interest in the project and influence over the site.

Fig.43: Stakeholder mapping Continental agricultural land use site

Stakeholders at this agricultural experimental site demonstrate a high level of interest in the ongoing research and project. This is likely due to their close connection to the site's activities, including sampling and research. However, the stakeholders are shown to have a low level of influence. While the site manager shows some influence on the site's economic, social, and environmental context, the overall influence of this stakeholder group remains limited. This is quite surprising given their role in the experimental site.

Despite their low influence, it is crucial to consult with these stakeholders. Their proximity to the experimental site and their involvement in agriculture

production, research, and soil sampling provide valuable insights and perspectives that can enhance the research and its impact.

Forest land use: stakeholder identification

Table 43 summarises the characteristics of the Continental forest land use site.

Continental forest land use site

Forest Land Use: Tree harvesting in deciduous forests Mission Soil: Sustainable management	
Extension	1 ha
Description geographical context	The sites are located in a hilly landscape south of Aachen, the nearest city. Deciduous forests dominate, featuring oak, birch, beech, rowan, hornbeam, and sycamore, occasionally interspersed with a few spruce trees. The ground consists of loamy soils with gravel, covered by distinct humus layers. The long-term average temperature is 9°C, with an annual precipitation of 836 mm.
Soil Health Pressures	Biodiversity loss, compaction, organic matter loss
Soil Health Practices	Reduction of tree harvest frequency
Intensity 1	Clear-cut 2018 followed by reforestation
Intensity 2	Thinning every 10 years (last time: 2019/2020)
Intensity 3	Managed succession (trees only cut for safety reasons)

Table 43: Continental forest land use site

The 6 stakeholders identified for the forest land use site are either identical to those of the agricultural site or are affiliated with the same organizations.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Site responsible Owners and managers of the agricultural site	Workers & Farmers	Management of the forest sites
NGO on agricultural or rural development	Civil society organisation	Management of the forest sites
Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Coordinator of experimental sites and public exchange
Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Organising the experimental sites and public exchange
Academics in agricultural, environmental science and economics	Education, Research	Scientific coordination of sampling and analysis
Academics in agricultural, environmental science and economics	Education, Research	Regional coordinator

Table 44: Stakeholder identification Continental forest land use site

Since the stakeholder categories for this site closely resemble those of the agricultural site, a description of each stakeholder group is not provided, yet the distribution is again shown in Figure 44.

Fig.44: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Continental forest land use site

Forest land use: stakeholder mapping

While the stakeholder groups for the agricultural and forest sites share some overlap, notable differences exist in their respective levels of interest and influence, as shown in Figure 45.

Fig.45: Stakeholder mapping Continental forest land use site

The mapping reveals that, while the interest and influence of workers & farmers and research centre remain consistent across both sites, the nature conservation foundation demonstrates slightly lower interest in the forest site compared to the agricultural site.

Mining land use: stakeholder identification

Table 45 summarises the characteristics of the Continental mining land use site.

Continental mining land use site

Mining Land Use: Opencast mining Mission Soil: Recultivation and renaturation	
Extension	1 ha
Description geographical context	The sites are part of a recultivation and renaturation program within a huge opencast mining area in the east of the city of Jülich. The colonization of plants and development of plant communities is left to natural processes. Younger sites are characterized by bushes and shrubs with broom. Some areas are cropped with lupine. Deciduous forests are developing in older sites. That area is characterized by sandy soils mixed with gravel.
Soil Health Pressures	Biodiversity loss, organic matter loss, contamination
Soil Health Practices	Transformation of landscape and land use from soil loss due to mining towards soil redeposition and forestry
Intensity 1	Recultivation 5 years after mining
Intensity 2	Recultivation 10 years after mining
Intensity 3	Recultivation 15 years after mining

Table 45: Continental mining land use site

5 stakeholders are identified for the mining land use site within the continental region.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Mining companies	Workers & Farmers	Opencast mining of the land and recultivation thereafter
Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Coordinator of experimental sites and public exchange
Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Organising the experimental sites and public exchange
Academics in agricultural, environmental science and economics	Education, Research	Scientific coordination of sampling and analysis
Academics in agricultural, environmental science and economics	Education, Research	Regional coordinator

Table 46: Stakeholder identification Continental mining land use site

The landscaping companies and the Thünen-Institute, previously encountered in other sites, are represented here as well.

Fig.46: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Continental mining land use site

Education, Research: The two stakeholders belonging to this site are part of the continental experimental site coordinator organisation, the Thünen-Institute.

Workers & Farmers: As in previous sites, the two stakeholders from the company responsible for site coordination and organization are present. A third stakeholder, representing the mining company operating at the site, has also been identified.

Mining land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 47 presents the interest and influence of the stakeholder categories for this site.

Fig.47: Stakeholder mapping Continental mining land use site

Similar to other continental sites, stakeholders demonstrate high interest but limited direct influence. It is important to note that the stakeholder representing the mining company displays a lower level of interest in the project while a higher impact on the site, particularly with regard to the site's environmental and economic impact.

Semi-natural land use: stakeholder identification

Table 47 summarises the characteristics of the Continental semi-natural land use site.

Continental semi-natural land use site

Semi-Natural Land Use: Grassland management Mission Soil: Reduction of mowing frequency and N-input	
Extension	1 ha
Description geographical context	The sites are situated in an agricultural landscape dotted with small villages, with Nideggen as the nearest town. The semi-natural sites have a high diversity of grassland plant species. This hilly region features a stony terrain with predominantly loamy soils. The long-term average temperature is 8.8°C, and the annual precipitation averages 600 mm.
Soil Health Pressures	Biodiversity loss, surplus N-input, organic matter loss
Soil Health Practices	Sustainable use of natural grassland by low mowing frequency per year and mitigated N-fertilisation
Intensity 1	Intensive N-fertilization and 3 cuts per year
Intensity 2	Only solid manure and 1-2 cuts per year
Intensity 3	No fertilization and only 1 cut per year

Table 47: Continental semi-natural land use site

A total of 6 stakeholders are identified in the semi-natural continental site.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Site responsible Owners and managers of the site	Workers & Farmers	Management of the semi-natural sites
NGO on agricultural or rural development	Civil society organisation	Management of the semi-natural sites
Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Coordinator of experimental sites and public exchange
Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Organising the experimental sites and public exchange
Academics in agricultural, environmental science and economics	Education, Research	Scientific coordination of sampling and analysis
Academics in agricultural, environmental science and economics	Education, Research	Regional coordinator

Table 48: Stakeholder identification Continental semi-natural land use site

These stakeholders again correspond to the categories and stakeholders identified in the previous continental sites.

Fig.48: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Continental semi-natural land use site

Semi-natural land use: stakeholder mapping

The stakeholder category map exhibits similarities to those of previous continental sites, as depicted in Figure 49, offering comparable insights.

Fig.49: Stakeholder mapping Continental mining land use site

Urban land use: stakeholder identification

Table 49 summarises the characteristics of the Continental urban land use site.

Continental urban land use site

Urban Land Use: Green space for leisure and aesthetic purposes Mission Soil: Frequency and scope of green space maintenance	
Extension	0.1 to 0,5 ha
Description geographical context	The sites are located in the centre of the small city of Eschweiler. Urban green spaces here are characterized by lawns, trees, and common weeds. The ground is highly compacted and characterized by clayey to loamy soils. The long-term average temperature is 9°C, with an annual precipitation of 836 mm.
Soil Health Pressures	Biodiversity loss, pollution (plastic dispersal), soil sealing
Soil Health Practices	Reduction of soil sealing by creating green spaces in urban areas
Intensity 1	Playground next to railway line. Area city park directly located at main road
Intensity 2	Lawn area with few shrubs and trees in front of residential buildings. Area of city park in distance of min. 50m to main road.
Intensity 3	Green strip with more shrubs and trees next to a sports field. Area of city park in a distance of min. 100m to main road.

Table 49: Continental urban land use site

A total of 5 stakeholders are identified in the urban continental site. Most stakeholders are also connected to other sites.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Opencast mining of the land and recultivation thereafter
Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Coordinator of experimental sites and public exchange
Landscaping companies	Workers & Farmers	Organising the experimental sites and public exchange
Academics in agricultural, environmental science and economics	Education, Research	Scientific coordination of sampling and analysis
Academics in agricultural, environmental science and economics	Education, Research	Regional coordinator

Table 50: Stakeholder identification Continental urban land use site

Figure 50 displays the distribution of stakeholders for this site.

Fig.50: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Continental urban land use site

Public bodies: This continental site stands out as the only one with a local public body stakeholder. This stakeholder works for the city of Eschweiler, where the urban site is located.

Urban land use: stakeholder mapping

Fig.51: Stakeholder mapping Continental urban land use site

Similar to other continental sites, the site workers and research institution show comparable levels of interest and influence. However, the local public body exhibits a higher level of influence, attributable to its involvement in local decision-making processes and its capacity to shape the site's characteristics and purpose.

8.1.5 Stakeholder identification and mapping Mediterranean sites

Agricultural land use: stakeholder identification

Table 51 summarises the characteristics of the Mediterranean agricultural land use site.

Mediterranean agricultural land use site

Agricultural Use: Cereal annual crops in a farm Mission Soil: yield optimization	
Extension	300 ha
Description geographical context	It is a very dry area with 250-350mm of annual precipitation, distributed in 2 periods along the year (spring and autumn). In winter there is long windy days reaching 100 km/h. The agricultural plots are located in a soft hills mixed with almonds and olive trees farms and bushes forest. We are in Ebro Valley where we can find typical calcareous soils with low soil organic matter levels.
Soil Health Pressures	Organic matter, erosion, soil structure & fertility loss
Soil Health Practices	Optimization management practices.
Intensity 1	Cereal cropping systems in rainfed conditions with intensive tillage. One deep tillage every 2 years and 3 superficial tillage. Sown every 2 years
Intensity 2	Cereal cropping systems in rainfed conditions with reduced tillage. Every year 3 times superficial tillage. Sown every year
Intensity 3	Cereal cropping systems in rainfed conditions with no-tillage more than 10 years. Sown every year

Table 51: Mediterranean agricultural land use site

A total of six stakeholders have been identified for the continental experimental site with agricultural land use.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Farmers and agricultural producers (livestock owners included)	Workers & Farmers	Group of farmers
Workers, former workers	Workers & Farmers	Farmer
Research bodies	Education, Research	Research
Agriculture newspapers	Media	Journalist
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Policy maker
Agricultural Industry Associations	Workers & Farmers	Cooperative of farmers

Table 52: Stakeholder identification Mediterranean agricultural land use site

Fig.52: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Mediterranean agricultural land use site

Education and Research: A single research institution is linked to this site, focusing on advancements and technological innovations in the agri-food sector.

Media: One journalist has been identified, contributing to an agricultural newspaper and covering relevant topics.

Public bodies: A policy-maker is associated with the site, holding a regional role as a key decision-maker in policy development.

Workers & Farmers: This category includes three stakeholders, comprising local farmers actively working on the site and a farmers' cooperative focused on the production and distribution of high-quality agricultural products.

Agricultural land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 53 maps the stakeholders of the agricultural Mediterranean site based on their interest and influence.

Fig.53: Stakeholder mapping Mediterranean agricultural land use site

The stakeholder mapping reveals that, apart from farmers, most stakeholder groups exhibit a generally high level of both influence and interest in this site. In particular, research institutions stand out with the highest levels of interest and influence. This can be attributed to their research involvement at the EU level, which provides them with broader scope and high-level expertise, and a high interest in BIOservicES. This stakeholder shows a significant influence over the environmental and social context of the site. Their position allows them to act as key stakeholder in the project's co-creation activities.

In contrast, farmers demonstrate lower levels of interest and influence. Their lower level of interest might be explained due to their localized focus and limited familiarity with European-level projects.

Dryland land use: stakeholder identification

Table 53 summarises the characteristics of the Mediterranean dryland land use site.

Mediterranean dryland land use site

Dryland Use: Pine and bushes forest Mission Soil: High or short land coverage	
Extension	40 ha
Description geographical context	Dryland areas are mixed with agricultural plots. Traditionally, low-slope areas were restored and cultivated, but nowadays, drylands are found on steep slopes or in difficult-to-plow terrains. The case of study is in a protected forest which pines were planted 80 years ago, the spontaneous species are bushes. The area is 635 m above sea level and 450 mm annual pluviometry.
Soil Health Pressures	Biodiversity and organic matter loss & erosion
Soil Health Practices	Optimize the dryland coverage
Intensity 1	Herbaceous vegetation
Intensity 2	Bush vegetation
Intensity 3	Woodland forest

Table 53: Mediterranean dryland land use site

The dryland experimental site in the Mediterranean biogeographical region has four stakeholders identified across four stakeholder groups.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Farmers and agricultural producers (livestock owners included)	Workers & Farmers	Lamb farmer
Research bodies	Education, Research	Research
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Decision maker
Rural Communities and Residents organizations	Residents, Citizens	Citizens association who uses dryland for trekking

Table 54: Stakeholder identification Mediterranean dryland land use site

Fig.54: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Mediterranean dryland land use site

Education and Research: The stakeholder in this category belongs to the same research institution identified in the agricultural site. Their primary focus is research and innovation in the agri-food sector, contributing expertise and insights at both regional and European levels.

Public Bodies: This stakeholder represents the regional council and plays a key role in regional decision-making processes, particularly in areas related to land use, agricultural policies, and environmental planning.

Residents and Citizens: A stakeholder from a local citizen association is identified. This group actively uses the dryland site for recreational activities, such as trekking, emphasizing the site's value for community engagement and leisure.

Workers and Farmers: This category includes one local farmer who is directly connected to the site. Their perspective is rooted in hands-on experience with the land.

Dryland land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 55 maps the stakeholder categories across their interest and influence in the project.

Fig.55: Stakeholder mapping Mediterranean dryland land use site

The stakeholder mapping reveals that research institutions exhibit the highest levels of influence and interest, likely fuelled by their expertise and active engagement in regional and EU-level research. The farmer and council member demonstrate slightly lower interest but maintain significant influence, particularly due to their economic and regional impact on the site. In contrast, the local citizen remains a peripheral stakeholder, with minimal involvement in core activities or decision-making processes.

Industrial land use: stakeholder identification

Table 55 summarises the characteristics of the Mediterranean industrial land use site.

Mediterranean industrial land use site

Industrial Use: Factories Mission Soil: industrial factories placement	
Extension	1 ha
Description geographical context	The industrial park is located in a gently sloping hill area, where some sections require significant land clearing. The primary soil is cover with bushes (rosemary, thyme, vulgaris,...) The altitude is 650 m. above sea level and 400 mm of annual pluviometry. In general, it is very clay soil. There are different industries with different soil pressures.
Soil Health Pressures	Biodiversity loss, erosion and pollution drift
Soil Health Practices	Nature restoration, biological walls.
Intensity 1	Soil in clay stockage industry
Intensity 2	Soil in logistic company
Intensity 3	Undisturbed, dense vegetal coverage

Table 55: Mediterranean industrial land use site

The industrial land use site has six stakeholders identified.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Site responsible Owners and managers of the industrial site	Workers & Farmers	Private company
Suppliers and subcontractors	Suppliers & Clients	Private company
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Policy maker
Industry Associations	Workers & Farmers	Companies association
Workers, former workers	Workers & Farmers	Private company
Transport and logistics companies	Suppliers & Clients	Private company

Table 56: Stakeholder identification Mediterranean industrial land use site

Figure 56 shows the distribution of stakeholder groups in this site.

Fig.56: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Mediterranean industrial land use site

Public bodies: This stakeholder represents a policymaker responsible for urban planning, playing a crucial role in shaping land use, infrastructure, and development strategies within the region.

Suppliers & Clients: This category includes two private companies. One operates in transport and logistics, providing essential supply chain services

while the other is a packaging company, contributing to the production processes linked to the site.

Workers & Farmers: This group includes three stakeholders. The site owner oversees the operations, while two factory workers are directly involved in the daily activities and contribute to the site's operational efficiency.

Industrial land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 57 maps the stakeholder categories across their interest and influence in the project.

Fig.57: Stakeholder mapping Mediterranean industrial land use site

The stakeholder mapping reveals that companies at the industrial site, along with their workers, exhibit generally low levels of interest and influence. Among the influence they do hold, their economic impact on the site stands out as their most significant contribution, though their overall influence remains limited. In contrast, the policymaker demonstrates a high level of influence due to their decision-making authority, making them a critical stakeholder to involve in co-creation activities.

Mining land use: stakeholder identification

Table 57 summarises the characteristics of the Mediterranean mining land use site.

Mediterranean mining land use site

Mining Use: Natural and agricultural restoration Mission Soil: Restoration management practices	
Extension	20 ha
Description geographical context	High coal mining has taken place in this area. The coal mines are located in "Val de Ariño" (550 masl) valley surrounded by "Sierra de Arcos" hills (800 masl). After coal exploitation, the ground is either well or poorly restored, leading to different natural outcomes.
Soil Health Pressures	Biodiversity, organic matter loss & erosion
Soil Health Practices	Ground clearing management and ground restoration.
Intensity 1	Unrestored
Intensity 2	Partially restored with cereal cropping
Intensity 3	Restored soil with woody trees (forest)

Table 57: Mediterranean mining land use site

The mining site includes four stakeholders across three categories, as shown in Table 58 and Figure 58.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Policy maker
Mining companies	Workers & Farmers	Extracting coal
Direct clients (cooperatives, farmers organizations...)	Suppliers & Clients	Farm
Mining companies	Workers & Farmers	Private company

Table 58: Stakeholder identification Mediterranean mining land use site

Fig.58: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Mediterranean mining land use site

Public Bodies: This stakeholder represents the local municipality and plays a key role in policy-making, influencing decisions that impact land use.

Suppliers & Clients: This stakeholder is a client utilizing the site for livestock farming. They rely on the land to support their agricultural operations.

Workers & Farmers: This group includes two mining companies operating on the site, employing a workforce engaged in resource extraction.

Mining land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 59 maps the stakeholders of the mining land use site across their interest in the project and influence over the site.

Fig.59: Stakeholder mapping Mediterranean mining land use site

The stakeholder mapping highlights that both the mining workers and the policy maker hold significant influence over the site, particularly in the economic context and profitability. Their involvement is crucial, as they have decision-making power that directly impacts the land management.

On the other hand, the farmer, while not a direct landowner, uses part of the site for livestock farming. As such, their level of influence is comparatively lower, which likely results in a reduced interest in the project's broader activities. Given that BIOServicES places a strong emphasis on agricultural activities, partners can share valuable insights and results with this stakeholder to help enhance sustainable farming practices.

Urban land use: stakeholder identification

Table 59 summarises the characteristics of the Mediterranean urban land use site.

Mediterranean urban land use site

Urban Use: Trees, grass and no human activities Mission Soil: Land management conservation	
Extension	0.5 ha
Description geographical context	Green areas in the town of Andorra are located between buildings. They usually have low slopes and are visited by walkers. All of them have artificial land cover; some are rain-fed, while others are irrigated.
Soil Health Pressures	Biodiversity loss
Soil Health Practices	Green areas design and management
Intensity 1	Intensive maintenance with grass coverage
Intensity 2	Ornamental tree coverage – without floor maintenance
Intensity 3	Unmanaged urban soil, sparse grass coverage

Table 59: Mediterranean urban land use site

The urban land use site in the Mediterranean region has identified five key stakeholders.

Identified Stakeholder type	Category	Role
Citizens and citizen organizations	Residents, citizens	Group of people buying food
Local residents' associations	Residents, citizens	People living in urban areas
Community gardeners	Workers & Farmers	Group of workers taking care of gardens
Site responsible / owners and entities owning the area	Workers & Farmers	Owner and building company
Government authorities and regulatory bodies (local, regional, national)	Public bodies	Mayor

Table 60: Stakeholder identification Mediterranean urban land use site

Figure 60 illustrates the distribution of these stakeholders across three distinct categories.

Fig.60: Distribution of identified stakeholder categories for the Mediterranean urban land use site

Public bodies: This stakeholder is the regional mayor, serving as the head of the municipality and playing a key role in local governance and policy-making.

Residents, Citizens: This category includes two stakeholders, including local residents living in the urban area and a citizens' association that focuses on promoting and selling locally grown foods and products.

Workers & Farmers: This group consists of one stakeholder representing a team of workers who manage the local gardens, as well as the site owner who oversees the land's overall management and use.

Urban land use: stakeholder mapping

Figure 61 maps the stakeholders of this site.

Fig.61: Stakeholder mapping Mediterranean urban land use site

The stakeholder mapping reveals varying levels of interest and influence across the different groups. The mayor demonstrates the highest level of both interest and influence, likely due to her pivotal decision-making role within the municipality that governs the urban site.

In contrast, community workers and local residents exhibit lower levels of interest in the project, which can be attributed to their more localized roles. However, community workers hold slightly more influence than residents, as they are directly involved in managing the site, particularly in maintaining the urban gardens.

While both groups play important roles in site management, community workers have a greater influence on the social aspects of the site. Their collaborative approach to local land management allows them to shape how the site is used, which directly impacts the community's relationship with the space

